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Predicting Signs of Cognitive Decline from Conversations with a Computerised Agent

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Declaration

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Abstract

Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) represents an intermediate stage between normal age-related cognitive changes and dementia. Early detection of MCI is critical, as it offers an opportunity for interventions that could slow progression to dementia. However, current clinical methods for detecting MCI are expensive, invasive, and resource-intensive. Speech-based biomarkers have emerged as a promising, non-invasive alternative for early detection of cognitive decline.

This research developed a multimodal machine learning pipeline to detect MCI from speech data. Acoustic and linguistic features were extracted from recordings of three cognitive tasks: Cookie Theft Description (CTD), Semantic Fluency Task (SFT), and Phonemic Fluency Task (PFT). Traditional machine learning classifiers (Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machines) and transformer-based models (BERT variants) were compared. The best result (macro-F1: 0.933) was achieved using a multimodal hierarchical ensemble pipeline combining acoustic and linguistic features on the CTD task. Among transformer models, ClinicalBERT achieved the highest performance on SFT task (macro-F1: 0.693), suggesting benefits from domain-specific pre-training. Additionally, this research was supported by a robust configuration-driven software framework developed to easily define, manage, and run complex experiments through simple YAML files, enabling rapid exploration and reproducibility — a valuable tool for future studies.

Acknowledgement

“The only source of knowledge is experience.” – Albert Einstein

I started this project with limited knowledge of machine learning and transformer models. Exploring this field was both a personal ambition and an opportunity to broaden my career perspective. Looking back, I am grateful for the journey and the knowledge gained.

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List of Acronyms

AD	Alzheimer’s Disease
MCI	Mild Cognitive Impairment
HC	Healthy Controls
MMSE	Mini-Mental State Examination
MoCA	Montreal Cognitive Assessment
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
PET	Positron Emission Tomography
CSF	Cerebrospinal Fluid
CTD	Cookie Theft Description
SFT	Semantic Fluency Task
PFT	Phonemic Fluency Task
ML	Machine Learning
NLP	Natural Language Processing
LR	Logistic Regression
SVM	Support Vector Machine
BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
LLM	Large Language Model
AUC	Area Under the Curve
ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristic
GeMAPS	Geneva Minimalistic Acoustic Parameter Set
eGeMAPS	Extended Geneva Minimalistic Acoustic Parameter Set
ComParE	Computational Paralinguistics Challenge
MFCC	Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients
PROCESS	Prediction and Recognition Of Cognitive declinE through Spontaneous Speech

Chapter 1

Introduction

Dementia is a general term that describes various medical conditions that significantly impair patients' cognitive functions, including memory, reasoning, and communication skills (Cunningham et al., 2015; Arvanitakis et al., 2019). Alzheimer's Disease (AD) is the most common cause of dementia, accounting for approximately 60–80% of cases (Alzheimer's Association, 2021). Dementia is a growing global health concern, with over 40 million individuals affected worldwide, a number projected to exceed 120 million by 2050 due to ageing populations (Tiwari et al., 2019, as cited in Huang et al. (2022)). In the United Kingdom, 1 in 11 people over the age of 65 have dementia (National Health Service, 2023), with total cases expected to rise from 982,000 to over 1.4 million by 2040 (Alzheimer's Society, 2024).

Mild cognitive impairment (MCI) represents an intermediate stage between normal age-related cognitive changes and dementia (Petersen and Negash, 2008). People diagnosed with MCI experience noticeable changes in their cognitive abilities but are not severe enough to interfere significantly with daily activities, as in the case of dementia (Petersen, 2016). Common symptoms in MCI patients include a deterioration in verbal fluency, including longer hesitations when speaking, difficulty in word retrieval, and changes in emotional responsiveness. Research shows that over 50% of those diagnosed with MCI may progress to dementia (especially AD) within five years (Poppe et al., 2020; Dunne et al., 2021). Therefore, early detection of MCI is critical, as it offers a window of opportunity for interventions that could slow progression to dementia and improve long-term outcomes (Yamasaki and Ikeda, 2024). However, this is a complex task due to its subtle symptoms, which often overlap with normal ageing, making it harder to diagnose than dementia (Sanford, 2017; Mirheidari et al., 2021).

Existing clinical methods for detecting MCI involve extensive cognitive testing, neuroimaging, or biomarker analysis, which can be expensive, invasive, time-intensive, and resource-heavy (McKhann et al., 2011). For example, clinical evaluations like neuropsychological assessments or imaging techniques (e.g., Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), Positron Emission Tomography (PET) scans) require significant expertise and infrastructure, making them less accessible for widespread use (Sabbagh et al., 2020).

While automated detection systems are emerging as alternatives, their development is often constrained by the use of limited or non-representative datasets. These datasets may lack the comprehensive metadata (like gender, age, and accent) necessary for robust diagnoses, given that such factors significantly impact cognitive performance. A case study by [Asperholm et al. \(2019\)](#) reveals that women often outperform men in episodic memory tasks (e.g., recalling a list of words, remembering details of a personal event), whereas men may have an advantage in certain spatial tasks (e.g., navigating a maze, assembling a puzzle). Therefore, automated systems that do not account for these conditions may generate results that are either too generalised or biased, reducing their effectiveness compared to traditional methods. There is a need for more accessible, efficient, and preferably automated methods for detecting cognitive decline.

Multiple studies have shown that speech-based cues can be used for detecting early signs of dementia ([Gosztolya et al., 2019](#); [Luz et al., 2021](#); [Mirheidari et al., 2021, 2023](#); [Agbavor and Liang, 2024](#); [Wang et al., 2025](#); [Zhang et al., 2025](#)). Subtle changes in speech patterns, such as hesitation, reduced speech rate, and word retrieval, are early signs of cognitive decline. Machine learning models can, therefore, be trained to detect MCI by analysing these speech patterns, offering a non-invasive and cost-effective approach to early diagnosis ([Luz et al., 2021](#); [Gosztolya et al., 2021](#)).

1.1 Aims and Objectives

The primary aim of this project was to develop and evaluate a robust pipeline for MCI detection using speech data (classifying between MCI and HC). To achieve this, the following objectives were set:

1. Utilize Natural Language Processing (NLP) and audio analysis tools to extract linguistic and acoustic features from manually transcribed speech data (text) and audio recordings.
2. Train and compare various traditional machine learning classifiers such as LR and SVMs using the extracted linguistic and acoustic features.
3. Fine-tune Large Language Models (LLMs) such as Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) and its variants (RoBERTa, DistilBERT and ClinicalBERT) as sequence classifiers for detecting cognitive decline.
4. Assess and compare the performance of various models to identify the most accurate and computationally efficient classifier for distinguishing between MCI and HC.

1.2 Overview of the Report

The following chapters provide a comprehensive examination of the project's development, research and findings so far and are structured as follows.

Chapter 2 – Literature Survey: Reviews existing methods for detecting cognitive decline, including clinical approaches, speech as a biomarker, traditional machine learning techniques, and large language models.

Chapter 3 – Data Analysis: Describes the dataset and explores the demographic distribution, class imbalance, and key characteristics across the three cognitive tasks used in this study.

Chapter 4 – Methodology: Outlines the research methodology, including data preprocessing, feature extraction approaches, model selection criteria, and ethical considerations.

Chapter 5 – Experimental Setup: Details the implementation of four modeling pipelines: acoustic ML, linguistic ML, transformer-based models, and a hierarchical ensemble approach.

Chapter 6 – Results and Discussion: Evaluates the performance of all pipelines across cognitive tasks, presents ablation studies, analyzes error patterns, and compares results with prior work.

Chapter 7 – Conclusions and Future Work: Summarizes key findings, acknowledges limitations, and outlines future research directions for speech-based cognitive assessment.

Chapter 2

Literature Review

This literature survey explores existing research on various methods and technologies used to detect cognitive decline. The survey begins by reviewing clinical methods for detecting cognitive decline, discussing their strengths and weaknesses. It then explores how speech can be used as a biomarker, focusing on linguistic, acoustic, and emotional features that change in people with MCI. Common speech-based tests, like the CTD and verbal fluency tests (SFT and PFT), are introduced to show how they capture patterns in speech which can be used to analyse cognitive decline. Following this, traditional machine learning techniques for speech analysis are examined, with an emphasis on their role in building predictive models. Additionally, LLMs are discussed, explaining the strengths of transformer models over traditional classifiers as they can capture complex patterns and context in text. Finally, a detailed comparison of related studies was performed, providing insights into what can be improved upon.

2.1 Clinical Methods for Detecting Cognitive Decline

This section reviews the existing clinical methods used to diagnose cognitive decline, including cognitive assessments, neuroimaging techniques, and biomarker analysis and their limitations.

2.1.1 Cognitive Assessments

The Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) is a widely used screening tool that assesses orientation, attention, memory, language, and visuospatial skills (Folstein et al., 1975). It consists of a 30-point questionnaire, with tasks such as recalling three words, counting backward, naming objects, and following simple commands. While MMSE is effective in screening for dementia, it has limitations in detecting MCI and exhibits education and cultural biases (Tombaugh and McIntyre, 1992). The Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) was developed to address these limitations. MoCA evaluates a broader range of cognitive functions and has shown higher sensitivity for detecting MCI. For example, the MMSE had a sensitivity of 18% for detecting MCI, whereas the MoCA successfully identified 90%

of MCI subjects (Nasreddine et al., 2005). Other domain-specific tests, such as the Wechsler Memory Scale (WMS) for memory and the Trail Making Test for executive function, provide more comprehensive assessments (Wechsler, 1997; Kabiri et al., 2023). Despite this, a study conducted by Brooks et al. (2008) reveals that WMS can misclassify healthy older adults as having MCI when relying solely on psychometric criteria based on WMS scores. In this study, approximately 26% of individuals aged 55–87 scored at or below the thresholds commonly associated with MCI in age-adjusted norms, and this rose to 39% when using demographically adjusted norms.

2.1.2 Neuroimaging Techniques

Neuroimaging plays a vital role in detecting structural and functional brain changes associated with cognitive decline. MRI can reveal atrophy (also known as cerebral atrophy) in key brain regions, such as the hippocampus and entorhinal cortex, which are affected early in AD (Jack et al., 2010). PET is a non-invasive imaging technique used to visualise and measure biological processes in the body, including brain activity and metabolism. PET scans using radioligands like Pittsburgh Compound B (PiB) can detect amyloid-beta plaques, a key feature of AD pathology (Klunk et al., 2004). Additionally, Fluorodeoxyglucose (FDG)-PET measures glucose metabolism, which is typically reduced in brain areas impacted by AD (Mosconi et al., 2008). These neuroimaging techniques can improve diagnostic accuracy and predict progression from MCI to dementia (Frisoni et al., 2010).

2.1.3 Biomarker Analysis

Biomarkers in Cerebrospinal Fluid (CSF) and blood have shown promise in the early diagnosis of cognitive decline. CSF levels of certain proteins, including amyloid-beta42, total tau, and phosphorylated tau, are altered in patients with AD (Blennow, 2017). However, collecting CSF is invasive, limiting its routine use. Blood-based biomarkers, such as neurofilament light chain (NfL) and plasma phosphorylated tau (p-tau), have gained significant attention as promising non-invasive alternatives to CSF (Zetterberg and Blennow, 2018). These biomarkers can be measured through a simple blood test, making them more accessible and practical for routine clinical use compared to CSF. Incorporating biomarker data with cognitive assessments and neuroimaging can enhance diagnostic precision and prognostic prediction (Jack Jr et al., 2018).

2.1.4 Limitations

Although there have been significant improvements in the current clinical methods for detecting cognitive decline, they still have several limitations. Cognitive assessments can be influenced by education, language, and cultural factors, leading to misdiagnosis (Ranson et al., 2019). Additionally, neuroimaging techniques are costly, may not be widely accessible, and could potentially expose individuals to radiation (Winblad et al., 2016). CSF biomarker analysis is invasive and may not be feasible for routine screening. Blood-based

biomarkers, while promising, require further validation and standardisation before clinical implementation (Molinuevo et al., 2018). These limitations highlight the need for more accessible, cost-effective, and non-invasive methods for early detection of cognitive decline.

In conclusion, clinical methods for detecting cognitive decline include cognitive assessments, neuroimaging techniques, and biomarker analysis. While each approach has strengths, it also has limitations related to cost, invasiveness, and accessibility. Future research should focus on developing robust and accessible solutions using non-invasive biomarkers for better diagnosis and prognosis of cognitive impairment.

2.2 Speech as a Biomarker for MCI

Speech has emerged as a promising approach for the early diagnosis of cognitive decline. This section discusses linguistic, acoustic, and emotional changes in MCI patients and highlights the importance of speech-based detection.

2.2.1 Linguistic Markers

Individuals with MCI often exhibit subtle changes in language use, including vocabulary, syntax complexity, and semantic content. Recent studies have employed various tasks to analyze these linguistic features, providing insights into early cognitive decline.

Hamrick et al. (2023) investigated lexical features in spontaneous speech among older adults, recruiting 39 participants who completed neuropsychological assessments and speech tasks, including CTD. They analyzed lexical properties such as speech rate, filler word usage, lexical frequency, and lexical diversity. Their analysis identified speech rate as the most reliable lexical indicator for distinguishing participants with MCI from healthy controls.

In another study by Cintoli et al. (2024), researchers analyzed verbal fluency patterns in 61 participants (aged 65-80) with amnesic MCI (aMCI) using phonemic and semantic fluency tasks. After 18 months, participants who converted to dementia produced significantly fewer clusters and switches between clusters compared to those who did not convert. These studies underscore the potential of linguistic analysis in identifying early signs of cognitive decline.

Tasks such as CTD and verbal fluency tests can reveal subtle language impairments. These tasks are a key part of this study and are discussed in [Section 2.3](#).

2.2.2 Acoustic Markers

In addition to linguistic changes, people with cognitive issues may exhibit distinct acoustic features in their speech. They may pause more often, speak slower, or sound less fluent. Yuan et al. (2021) showed that hesitations like “uh” and “um” were more frequent in patients with AD. Similarly, Gosztolya and Tóth (2024) demonstrated that combining standard acoustic feature sets with custom attributes focusing on silent and filled pauses can effectively distinguish MCI patients from healthy controls. Furthermore, Huang et al. (2024) found that

acoustic features such as pitch, jitter, shimmer, and Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC) are valuable in differentiating between AD, MCI, and healthy controls. Their results showed that people with cognitive decline spoke with less control over tone and volume. These differences show up even in short conversations and can help detect early signs of decline without invasive tests.

These findings highlight the potential of acoustic markers as valuable tools for detecting cognitive decline. Machine learning models can learn patterns from these acoustic features and effectively classify MCI and HC, offering a non-invasive solution.

2.2.3 Emotional Changes in MCI Patients

Emotional expression in speech has also been found to differ between MCI patients and healthy controls, with MCI often showing differences in how they express and perceive emotions in their speech. They often have trouble expressing and understanding emotions in speech. Their voices may sound flat, and they might struggle to recognize emotions like happiness or sadness in others' voices.

For example, earlier study by [Taler and Phillips \(2008\)](#) found that MCI patients tend to have reduced emotional expressiveness in their speech, meaning their tone and delivery may lack emotion, sounding flat or monotone. This is referred to as a “flat effect”. Additionally, [Han et al. \(2018\)](#) discovered that MCI patients struggle both to recognize emotions in others' speech (such as identifying happiness, sadness, or anger) and to convey their own emotions effectively. These difficulties may result from changes in the brain areas responsible for processing emotions and understanding social interactions, which are often affected by MCI. This means that emotional and social aspects of communication, not just memory or language, can be impacted by MCI. Furthermore, in a recent study by [Amlerova et al. \(2022\)](#), they evaluated emotional prosody recognition (EPR) in participants with aMCI, AD, and healthy controls. They used a standardized task where participants identified emotions conveyed through tone of voice. The results showed that both aMCI and AD groups scored significantly lower on EPR tasks compared to healthy controls.

2.2.4 Advantages of Speech-Based Detection

Speech-based detection of MCI offers several advantages over traditional diagnostic methods. First, speech analysis is non-invasive and does not require costly or time-consuming procedures, such as neuroimaging or extensive neuropsychological testing ([Subsection 2.1.2](#)). Second, speech data can be easily collected through simple audio recordings ([Mirheidari et al., 2021](#)), making it a cost-effective and scalable approach for large-scale screening. Finally, machine learning algorithms can be used to automate speech-based detection ([Gosztolya et al., 2019](#); [Luz et al., 2021](#); [Mirheidari et al., 2021, 2023](#); [Gosztolya and Tóth, 2024](#); [Zhang et al., 2025](#); [Wang et al., 2025](#)), enabling accurate and efficient processing, even on large datasets.

In summary, the insights drawn from the linguistic, acoustic, and emotional changes

in the speech of MCI patients prove that speech is indeed an excellent biomarker for detecting cognitive decline. Speech-based detection is non-invasive, effective, and scalable, demonstrating an advantage over clinical detection methods.

2.3 Speech-Based Cognitive Assessments

Speech-based cognitive assessments, like the Cookie Theft Description Task and Verbal Fluency Tests, are essential tools for analysing subtle changes in speech patterns of MCI patients. These tasks evaluate various cognitive domains, including language, memory, and executive function, providing valuable insights into both linguistic and non-linguistic impairments. This section explores these two assessments and their relevance in identifying cognitive decline.

2.3.1 The Cookie Theft Description Task

Figure 2.1: The “Cookie Theft picture” from the Boston Diagnostic Aphasia Examination Third Edition (BDAE-3) (Goodglass et al., 2001).

The Cookie Theft task is a popular speech-based cognitive assessment tool used in both clinical and research settings to evaluate an individual’s language production, spontaneous speech, and narrative coherence which provides valuable insights into their cognitive abilities (Drummond et al., 2015; Hamrick et al., 2023). In this task, participants are typically

presented with a picture (Figure 2.1) from the Boston Diagnostic Aphasia Examination – Third Edition, commonly known as the “Cookie Theft” picture. The image depicts a kitchen scene where a boy and a girl steal cookies from a jar while their mother is distracted. During the task, participants are asked to describe what they observe in the picture. This open-ended prompt allows for the assessment of various cognitive domains, including attention (ability to focus on and interpret the scene), memory (recalling and integrating elements), language (word retrieval, sentence formulation), and executive function (organization and sequencing of the narrative) (Forbes-McKay and Venneri, 2005).

Relevance for Cognitive Decline Detection

The Cookie Theft task has proven effective in capturing impairments associated with cognitive decline, such as those observed in MCI and dementia (Mirheidari et al., 2021, 2023). Individuals with MCI or dementia often exhibit difficulties in both linguistic and non-linguistic aspects of the task (Drummond et al., 2015). Linguistic impairments observed in the Cookie Theft task may include word-finding difficulties, reduced syntactic complexity, and grammatical errors. Non-linguistic impairments may involve reduced attention to detail, difficulty sequencing events, and overall lack of information in the description (Mueller et al., 2018). The Cookie Theft task serves as a standardized tool across clinical and research settings, allowing for consistent assessment and comparison of cognitive abilities in various populations and languages (Gosztolya et al., 2021).

2.3.2 Verbal Fluency Tests

Verbal fluency tests are another common speech-based assessment used to evaluate cognitive functions. These tests measure an individual’s ability to generate words under specific constraints, typically within a given time limit. There are two main types of verbal fluency tests: phonemic fluency and semantic fluency. In phonemic fluency tasks, participants are asked to produce as many words as possible that begin with a specific letter, such as “F”, “A”, or “S”, within a given time limit, usually one minute. Semantic fluency tasks, on the other hand, require participants to generate words belonging to a particular semantic category, such as animals or fruits, within the same time constraint (Shao et al., 2014).

Verbal fluency tests assess various cognitive domains, including lexical retrieval (the ability to access and retrieve words from one’s mental lexicon), executive function (the ability to strategize, switch between subcategories, and avoid repetition), and working memory (the ability to keep track of previously generated words) (Shao et al., 2014).

Relevance for Cognitive Decline Detection

Multiple studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of verbal fluency tests in differentiating between healthy controls, individuals with MCI, and those with dementia (Drummond et al., 2015; Gosztolya et al., 2021; Mirheidari et al., 2023). Reduced output, slower response times, and increased errors are commonly observed in MCI and dementia groups (König et al.,

2015). Interestingly, semantic fluency tasks have been found to be more sensitive to early cognitive decline than phonemic fluency tasks. This difference is thought to arise from the greater reliance of semantic fluency on temporal lobe function, which is often affected early in the case of Alzheimer’s disease and other dementias (Wright et al., 2023). In contrast, phonemic fluency appears to be more dependent on frontal lobe function, which may be relatively preserved in the early stages of cognitive decline.

In conclusion, speech-based assessments are valuable tools. The Cookie Theft task and verbal fluency tests provide complementary information about an individual’s cognitive functioning. While the Cookie Theft task offers a more comprehensive assessment of language production and narrative coherence, verbal fluency tests provide a focused evaluation of lexical retrieval and executive function. Together, these tasks contribute to a multimodal assessment framework for detecting and monitoring cognitive decline. Future research can therefore explore the use of automated tools and machine learning techniques to analyse both linguistic and acoustic features extracted from these tasks.

2.4 Machine Learning for Automatic Detection

This section focuses on how ML is applied in healthcare, with a specific emphasis on supervised learning techniques. These methods are widely used for classification tasks, and are crucial to this project’s aim of distinguishing between MCI and HC. It introduces key concepts and algorithms, focusing on their potential to improve diagnostic accuracy and support clinical decision-making. It also highlights the advantages and limitations of these algorithms. Understanding these algorithms is critical for selecting the most appropriate models for this project.

2.4.1 Machine Learning in Healthcare

Machine Learning is transforming healthcare by providing tools that help medical professionals make more accurate and informed decisions. By leveraging vast amounts of data, ML algorithms can identify patterns and make predictions with remarkable accuracy. In healthcare, ML can be used to analyse patient records, imaging data, and other medical information to find patterns that might not be immediately visible to doctors. These patterns can help identify diseases earlier, predict patient outcomes, and recommend personalized treatments, making medical care more efficient and effective.

One prominent example is the IBM Watson Health (Chen et al., 2016), which has recently been rebranded as Merative. This system uses advanced ML techniques to tackle complex medical challenges. For example, in oncology (the study and treatment of cancer), it can process vast amounts of research and patient data to recommend potential treatment options tailored to individual patients. Similarly, in genomics (the study of genes and their functions), ML helps identify genetic mutations that might be linked to specific diseases.

These capabilities highlight how ML is not just a theoretical tool but a practical technology that is already being used to improve healthcare.

Limitations of ML Application in Healthcare

It is also crucial to highlight some of the challenges in the application of ML in healthcare, particularly for speech-based diagnostics. One significant issue is potential bias in ML models, which arises when models are trained on datasets that are non-representative or lack detailed metadata and demographic information. For instance, models that are trained on only English-speaking datasets might struggle to accurately diagnose cognitive impairment in those who speak different languages or dialects.

Data scarcity is another recurring problem. Due to privacy and ethical concerns, it can be challenging to collect and share large, high-quality datasets, especially for conditions like cognitive decline that require specialized data collection protocols. For example, gathering speech data often involves lengthy interviews or tasks such as the assessments discussed in [Section 2.3](#), which can be time-consuming for participants to complete. Moreover, participants must give informed consent, and data must be carefully anonymized and secured, further limiting the scale and accessibility of datasets for ML research.

Finally, integrating speech-based ML systems into real-world clinical workflows poses additional challenges. To be practical tools for healthcare professionals, these systems need to process data efficiently and generate predictions in a timely manner to enable their integration into fast-paced clinical settings ([Nagendran et al., 2020](#)).

2.4.2 Supervised Machine Learning

Figure 2.2: An Overview of Different Types of Machine Learning Techniques

Machine learning covers a range of approaches ([Figure 2.2](#)), such as unsupervised learning, reinforcement learning, and supervised learning, each serving different purposes. However,

for this project, the focus is specifically on supervised machine learning, particularly binary classification, as it aligns with our goal of distinguishing between MCI and HC.

In supervised learning, algorithms are trained on labeled datasets, where the desired output (e.g., diagnosis) is known for each input (e.g., patient data). By learning from these labeled examples, the algorithm can generalize and make predictions on new, unseen data. Supervised learning is widely used in medical diagnostics, enabling the development of models that can accurately detect various conditions, including cognitive decline, cancer, diabetes, and cardiovascular diseases (Kourou et al., 2015; Oikonomou and Khera, 2023).

2.4.3 Traditional Classification Algorithms

Logistic Regression

Figure 2.3: LR Sigmoid Function

Logistic Regression (LR) is a simple classification algorithm designed to predict the probability that a given input belongs to a particular category or class. For example, it can determine whether an email is spam or not spam or whether a patient has a certain condition or not (MCI or HC). LR uses a mathematical function called the logistic function (or sigmoid function) to map input values to a probability value between 0 and 1. The logistic function is defined as:

$$P(y = 1|x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_n x_n)}} \quad (2.1)$$

where $P(y = 1|x)$ represents the probability of the input x belonging to class 1, β_0 is the intercept (or bias term), and $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_n$ are the coefficients corresponding to the input

features x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n .

In [Figure 2.3](#), the horizontal axis represents the input values (x). This input could be a single feature or a weighted sum of multiple features ($w^T x + b$, where w is the weight vector and b is the bias). The vertical axis represents the predicted probability (P), i.e the output of the sigmoid function. The red dashed line represents the **threshold** (usually set at $P = 0.5$). Inputs with probabilities above this are classified as one class, while those below are classified as the other class. For example, if $P(x) > 0.5$, the input is classified as Class 1, otherwise classified as Class 2. The gray dashed line represents the **decision boundary** in the input feature space. This is the value of x (or $w^T x + b = 0$) where the model switches from predicting Class 0 to Class 1. For 1D data (i.e one input feature), it's a vertical line (or hyperplane for multiple-dimensional data).

A systematic review by [Issitt et al. \(2022\)](#) compared the classification performance of logistic regression and neural networks (NN) across 21 clinical studies using identical datasets. The review found that neural networks outperformed logistic regression in 62% of the studies, but the average improvement in performance was small—about 0.03. The confidence interval ranged from 0.00 to 0.06, meaning the true benefit of using neural networks could be minimal in many real-world cases. The authors concluded that while NNs may offer slight performance benefits in some scenarios, LR models remain a practical and interpretable option for many healthcare applications, particularly when simplicity and transparency are important.

K-Nearest Neighbors

Figure 2.4: Before KNN Classification: visualizing the impact of K on the decision, showing potential outcomes for $K = 3$ and $K = 7$.

Figure 2.5: After KNN Classification: the new data point is classified as Class B using $K=3$, based on the majority vote of its nearest neighbours.

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) is a non-parametric classification and regression algorithm. It is

based on the idea that similar data points tend to have similar output values or class labels. In classification, KNN makes predictions for new, unseen data points by looking at the K closest data points in the training set and assigning the majority class. For example, imagine you have a scatterplot where each point represents a data sample (as shown in [Figure 2.4](#)), and each point belongs to one of two classes (red or green). If we want to classify new, unseen data point (shown as a yellow datapoint), the KNN algorithm works as follows:

1. Choose a value for K (e.g $K = 3$), which represents the number of nearest neighbours to consider for majority voting.
2. Calculate the distance between that point and all the data points in the training set. Common distance metrics include Euclidean distance, Manhattan distance, or Minkowski distance.
3. Select the K data points from the training set that are closest to the new data point based on the calculated distances.
4. Determine the class label of the new data point by taking a majority vote among the K nearest neighbours.
5. Repeat steps 2-4 for all new, unseen data points that may need to be classified.

Interestingly, the choice of K can affect the results. For instance, in [Figure 2.5](#), if $K = 7$ were chosen, the new yellow data point would be classified as A. Larger K values often make the model more robust to noise but may miss local patterns. KNN is intuitive, easy to implement, and can handle multi-class classification problems. However, it can struggle with high-dimensional data (due to the curse of dimensionality) and requires careful tuning of K ([Halder et al., 2024](#)).

Support Vector Machines

Support Vector Machines (SVM) are powerful classification algorithms that aim to find the optimal hyperplane that separates different classes in a high-dimensional feature space. In simpler terms, SVM tries to draw a line (in 2D) or a plane (in 3D or higher) that best separates the different groups of data points. Imagine you have a scatter plot with two different types of data points, represented by blue circles and red squares. The goal is to find the best line that separates the blue circles from the red squares while keeping the largest possible distance from the nearest points of each class. In the [Figure 2.6](#):

- The solid black line is the maximum-margin hyperplane (decision boundary) that best separates the two classes.
- The dashed gray lines are the margins, which are equidistant from the hyperplane.
- The green-outlined points (one circle and one square) that lie closest to the margins are called the support vectors.

Figure 2.6: SVM on a linearly separable dataset, highlighting the decision boundary (hyperplane), margins, and support vectors (data points with green outline)

The SVM algorithm finds the hyperplane that maximizes the distance (margin) between the support vectors of each class. This hyperplane serves as the decision boundary for classifying new, unseen data points. If a new point falls on one side of the hyperplane, it is classified as a blue circle; if it falls on the other side, it is classified as a red square. The decision function for a binary SVM classifier is given by:

$$f(x) = \text{sign} \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i y_i K(x_i, x) + b \right) \quad (2.2)$$

where α_i are the learned coefficients, y_i are the class labels, $K(x_i, x)$ is the kernel function representing the similarity between the support vector x_i and the input x , and b is the bias term.

For data that is not linearly separable (e.g., when the groups overlap or are curved), SVM uses a technique called the **kernel trick**. This maps the data into a higher-dimensional space where it becomes easier to separate the groups with a hyperplane. Furthermore, while SVMs are powerful for handling high-dimensional data, they initially presented some challenges. A key drawback was that standard SVMs only provided class predictions without inherent probability estimates. However, these problems have been addressed with the emergence of modern machine learning libraries like scikit-learn¹, which offers probability estimates when

¹SVM Documentation: <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.svm.SVC.html>

the `probability` parameter is set during initialization.

Other Algorithms

Other classification algorithms include Naive Bayes and Decision Trees. Naive Bayes is a probabilistic classifier that assumes independence among features and uses Bayes' theorem to compute class probabilities. It is particularly effective for text classification tasks, such as spam detection and sentiment analysis, due to its simplicity and efficiency. Decision Trees are hierarchical models that make predictions by traversing a tree-like structure based on input values. They are good for handling both categorical and numerical data, are non-parametric, and provide interpretable models. Each algorithm has its strengths and limitations, and selecting the most suitable one often depends on the nature of the dataset, the problem requirements, and computational constraints.

2.4.4 Ensemble Algorithms

Ensemble learning is a broad term for methods that combine predictions from multiple models to improve overall performance (Sagi and Rokach, 2018). The basic principle behind ensemble learning is that by aggregating the outputs of diverse models, the collective decision can be more accurate and robust than individual models. Common ensemble techniques include bagging (bootstrap aggregating), boosting, and stacking, each of which has distinct methods for combining models to optimize performance.

- **Bagging (Bootstrap Aggregating):** Bagging trains multiple models on random subsets of the data and combines their predictions to reduce variance. By averaging predictions or using majority voting, bagging stabilizes the model and reduces overfitting. It works well for unstable algorithms like decision trees, where small changes in the data can lead to significantly different outcomes.
- **Boosting:** Boosting is another popular ensemble method, but unlike bagging, it focuses on correcting the errors of previous models. Models are trained sequentially, and each new model gives more weight to the data points that previous models misclassified. Algorithms like AdaBoost and Gradient Boosting (e.g., XGBoost, LightGBM) are widely used boosting methods. Boosting is particularly effective for achieving high accuracy but can be more prone to overfitting if not carefully tuned.
- **Stacking:** Stacking takes ensemble learning a step further by combining predictions from multiple base models using a meta-model. The base models are trained independently, and their outputs are used as inputs to a second-level model (meta-model), which learns how to combine these predictions. Stacking can leverage the strengths of different types of models, such as decision trees, SVMs, and neural networks, to create a more powerful final model.

Voting Classifiers: Hard and Soft Voting

Soft (probability-averaging) and hard (majority) voting are common aggregation strategies in ensemble methods such as Bagging or in standalone voting classifiers. In hard voting, each model casts one vote for a class label, and the class with the majority of votes is selected—this approach treats all models equally without considering prediction confidence. In soft voting, each model outputs a probability for each class, and the final prediction is based on the average probabilities across models, which tends to perform better when models are well-calibrated. [Jabbar \(2024\)](#) applied both methods to network intrusion detection and found that the soft voting classifier achieved an accuracy of 99.967%, while the hard voting classifier reached 100%, showing the value of combining predictions across diverse models.

Advantages and Disadvantages of Ensemble Methods

Ensemble methods offer several advantages, including improved accuracy, robustness to noise and outliers, and better generalization to unseen data ([Sagi and Rokach, 2018](#); [Jabbar, 2024](#)). By combining diverse models, ensembles can capture different aspects of the data and reduce the impact of individual model biases. However, ensemble methods also have some disadvantages. They can be computationally expensive, especially when training and combining a large number of models. Ensembles also introduce additional complexity and may reduce the interpretability of the final predictions compared to single models.

2.5 Transition to Large Language Models

Machine learning and NLP have undergone major transformations over the years. Traditional machine learning models, which rely heavily on manually transformed numerical features, are now being replaced by LLMs. Unlike traditional models, language models excel at understanding context and meaning in text, making them particularly useful for analyzing text data from cognitive tests. This section introduces LLMs, focusing on how they work, their advantages, and their potential for detecting cognitive decline from speech data. It also compares LLMs to traditional models, highlighting key differences and benefits.

2.5.1 Introduction to LLMs

Large Language Models (LLMs) are deep learning models trained on large amounts of text to understand and generate human language. They use billions of parameters and are designed to capture patterns in grammar, meaning, and context. LLMs are based on the Transformer architecture, introduced by [Vaswani et al. \(2017\)](#), which replaces older, sequential models with a more efficient self-attention mechanism. This design allows the model to learn contextual relationships across entire sequences in parallel, resulting in deeper linguistic understanding. This innovation formed the basis for modern LLMs like BERT and GPT (Generative Pre-trained Transformer).

The Transformer Architecture

Figure 2.7: The Transformer architecture (Vaswani et al., 2017), showing the encoder (left) and decoder (right) stack with self-attention and feed-forward layers.

The Transformer architecture (see Figure 2.7) is based on an encoder-decoder structure, although many large language models use only one of the two components. For example, BERT uses only the encoder, while GPT uses only the decoder. Each encoder layer contains two sub-layers: a multi-head self-attention mechanism and a position-wise fully connected feed-forward network. These sub-layers are wrapped in residual connections and followed by layer normalization. All sub-layer outputs and embedding layers share the same dimensionality to support residual connections.

Self-attention allows the model to relate different positions of a single input sequence to compute a contextualized representation. It operates on a set of queries (Q), keys (K), and values (V), all packed into matrices and derived from the same input. The attention mechanism computes similarity scores between queries and keys, scales them by the square root of the key dimension, and applies a softmax to obtain weights for combining the values. The formula for scaled dot-product attention is given as:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax} \left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}} \right) V \quad (2.3)$$

where $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d_k}$, $K \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d_k}$, $V \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d_v}$, and d_k is the dimensionality of the keys. This formulation allows the model to efficiently compute interactions between all tokens in the

sequence in parallel.

Transformer-based LLMs are now widely used in tools like chatbots, translation systems, and text summarizers. They are also useful for classifying documents and answering questions. In healthcare, LLMs can analyze conversational data from cognitive tests to detect cognitive decline. While traditional machine learning models have been used to extract and analyze linguistic features, LLMs take this further by leveraging their deep contextual understanding of text. For example, unlike earlier models that rely on predefined features, LLMs can automatically learn from text data, simplifying the training process.

2.5.2 BERT and its Variants

BERT is a transformer-based model introduced by [Devlin et al. \(2019\)](#) that uses only the encoder portion of the Transformer architecture ([Vaswani et al., 2017](#)). Unlike earlier models that process text left-to-right or right-to-left, BERT uses a bidirectional attention mechanism. This means it examines a word in the context of all other words in a sentence, both before and after it. This bidirectional approach allows it to learn deep contextual relationships between words in a sentence.

BERT is pre-trained using two objectives: Masked Language Modeling (MLM) and Next Sentence Prediction (NSP). In MLM, some input tokens are randomly replaced with a [MASK] token, and the model is trained to predict the original token. This helps BERT learn from both left and right context. In NSP, the model is given a pair of sentences and must predict whether the second sentence follows the first, helping it understand sentence relationships.

To process input text, BERT combines three types of embeddings for each token: a **token embedding**, which captures the meaning of the word; a **segment embedding**, which indicates whether a token belongs to the first or second sentence in a pair; and a **position embedding**, which encodes the position of the token in the sequence. These three vectors are summed together to form the final input representation. Additionally, special tokens are used to structure the input. The [CLS] token is added at the beginning of the input sequence and is used to represent the entire sentence pair for classification tasks. The [SEP] token is used to mark the boundary between two sentences and to signal the end of the sequence. This full input representation is illustrated in [Figure 2.8](#).

BERT comes in two main model sizes. BERT_{BASE} has 12 Transformer layers (also called encoder blocks), a hidden size of 768, and 12 attention heads, totaling 110 million parameters. BERT_{LARGE} doubles these values with 24 layers, a hidden size of 1024, and 16 attention heads, resulting in 340 million parameters.

Variants of BERT

Since the introduction of BERT, numerous variants have been developed to address specific domains, enhance performance, or improve efficiency. [Table 2.1](#) lists some notable BERT variants.

Figure 2.8: BERT input representation (Devlin et al., 2019). Each token’s input embedding is the sum of token, segment, and position embeddings.

Table 2.1: Variants of BERT

Domain-Specific	Enhanced	Compressed	Multilingual
ClinicalBERT	RoBERTa	DistilBERT	XLNet
BioBERT	ALBERT	TinyBERT	mBERT
SciBERT	ELECTRA	MobileBERT	XLNet
PubMedBERT	SpanBERT	MiniLM	MuRIL

This project also explore using BERT, including variants like RoBERTa, DistilBERT and ClinicalBERT as sequence classifiers for detecting cognitive decline.

- **RoBERTa:**² An enhanced version of BERT that improves training strategies for better results (Liu et al., 2019). By modifying key hyperparameters in BERT, RoBERTa can handle larger amounts of training data.
- **DistilBERT:**³ A smaller, faster, and cheaper variant of BERT, trained with 40% fewer parameters but still preserves over 95% of BERT’s original performance (Sanh et al., 2019). By using knowledge distillation techniques, DistilBERT reduces the model size and computational requirements, making it more suitable for resource-constrained environments or real-time applications.
- **ClinicalBERT:**⁴ A domain-specific adaptation of BERT, trained on clinical texts such as electronic health records (EHRs) and medical notes. (Huang et al., 2019). By leveraging the language patterns and terminology specific to the clinical domain, ClinicalBERT has shown promising results in tasks like named entity recognition and relation extraction in medical texts.

²RoBERTa on HuggingFace: <https://huggingface.co/FacebookAI/roberta-base>

³DistilBERT on HuggingFace: <https://huggingface.co/distilbert/distilbert-base-uncased>

⁴ClinicalBERT on HuggingFace: https://huggingface.co/emilyalsentzer/Bio_ClinicalBERT

2.5.3 Comparison of LLMs to Traditional Models

LLMs such as BERT and its variants, offer significant advantages over traditional machine learning models like LR, SVMs and KNN. Traditional models heavily depend on manual feature engineering by domain experts, which requires deep knowledge and effort to identify relevant features for a given task. In simpler terms, traditional models cannot directly interpret raw data, especially unstructured data like text, images, or audio. Instead, they require the data to be transformed into a numerical format that highlights relevant patterns or characteristics. This transformation process is known as feature engineering and is often done manually by humans who have expertise in the problem domain. However, modern tools and libraries, such as OpenSMILE, have significantly streamlined this process and is discussed in the next section.

LLMs, on the other hand, are pre-trained on massive datasets, enabling them to capture rich linguistic patterns and encode general knowledge from diverse contexts. This pre-training allows LLMs to directly learn complex features from the input data, bypassing the need for manual feature engineering and offering a more flexible approach to handling diverse datasets (Devlin et al., 2019). Another advantage of LLMs is their ability to scale and adapt to specific tasks. They can be fine-tuned with relatively small amounts of labeled data, making them particularly effective for domain-specific applications (Devlin et al., 2019). Furthermore, LLMs exhibit robustness when working with imbalanced datasets, a common issue in fields like healthcare, where detecting rare conditions such as cognitive decline is crucial (Oikonomou and Khera, 2023).

Despite these advantages, LLMs come with certain challenges that must be considered. Their high computational requirements demand significant resources, such as GPUs and large memory capacities, which can be a barrier for smaller organizations or resource-constrained settings (Sanh et al., 2019). Additionally, the performance of LLMs is highly dependent on the quality and quantity of the pre-training data. If the data does not adequately represent the target domain, the model's effectiveness can be compromised (Huang et al., 2019). Moreover, LLMs often function as “black boxes,” making it difficult to interpret their decision-making processes. In contrast, traditional models like LR provide greater transparency and interpretability, which can be critical in applications where understanding model decisions is essential (Issitt et al., 2022).

In summary, LLMs have demonstrated remarkable performance in various NLP tasks, including applications like detecting cognitive decline. However, their computational demands, dependency on data quality, and interpretability limitations must be carefully considered. Choosing between language and traditional models ultimately depends on the specific requirements and constraints of the application at hand.

2.6 Tools, Libraries and Frameworks

This section explores the various tools and libraries commonly used for acoustic and linguistic feature extraction, as well as those used for model training, fine-tuning, and data visualization in the context of detecting cognitive decline from speech data.

2.6.1 Acoustic Feature Extraction with OpenSMILE

OpenSMILE (Open-Source Speech and Music Interpretation by Large-Space Extraction) is a widely used toolkit for extracting acoustic features from audio signals, including speech and pathological speech (Eyben et al., 2010), which is particularly relevant for cognitive impairment studies where speech-based biomarkers are analyzed to distinguish between MCI and HC. Its flexibility and comprehensive feature sets and levels make it a popular choice for researchers working on machine learning applications in this domain.

Feature Sets

Feature sets in OpenSMILE represent predefined collections of features designed for specific tasks or research goals. Each feature set contains a group of acoustic features tailored to different levels of detail and interpretability. These include:

- **Geneva Minimalistic Acoustic Parameter Set (GeMAPS):** This low-dimensional feature set contains 62 features focusing on interpretable parameters like pitch, energy, and harmonicity, which are crucial for studying speech affected by cognitive impairments. GeMAPS balances simplicity and effectiveness, making it ideal for smaller datasets or lightweight models.
- **Extended Geneva Minimalistic Acoustic Parameter Set (eGeMAPS):** Building on GeMAPS, eGeMAPS adds additional 26 features, including prosodic and spectral features. This comprehensive set provides deeper insights into speech patterns, such as variability in pitch or changes in voice quality, which are often observed in MCI patients.
- **Computational Paralinguistics Challenge (ComParE):** A high-dimensional feature set with 6,373 features. ComParE is suitable for advanced models capable of handling large feature spaces. It captures a wide range of acoustic parameters, including MFCCs, making it ideal for exploratory research or tasks requiring detailed acoustic analysis.

Feature Levels

Feature Levels dictate how features are processed and represented. OpenSMILE feature levels include:

- **Low-Level Descriptors (LLDs):** Represent raw, frame-by-frame measurements of acoustic properties such as pitch, energy, or Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs). LLDs provide a detailed, time-sensitive representation of the audio signal, useful for examining moment-to-moment variations in speech.
- **Functionals:** These summarize LLDs over a specified time window, calculating statistical measures like mean, standard deviation, or range. Functionals are crucial for creating fixed-length feature vectors suitable for machine learning models.

By combining these feature sets and levels, OpenSMILE provides a robust framework for extracting meaningful acoustic markers from audio recordings.

2.6.2 Linguistic Feature Extraction Tools and Techniques

Text embeddings are dense vector representations of textual data that encode semantic meaning and syntactic structure. These embeddings transform text into numerical formats, serving as input features for machine learning models that cannot process raw text directly. All downstream traditional models in this study utilize embeddings generated with the **sentence-transformers**⁵ framework (Reimers and Gurevych, 2019), chosen for its flexibility in handling different embedding strategies suitable for varied linguistic tasks.

Sentence Transformers

The **sentence-transformers** library provides a versatile approach to generating text embeddings. It can leverage models specifically fine-tuned for optimal sentence-level representations, such as Sentence-BERT (SBERT) variants or models like **nomic-ai/modernbert-embed-base**⁶. These sentence-specific models are good at capturing the nuances of sentence meaning, context, and coherence. This capability is particularly advantageous for tasks like the Cookie Theft task where understanding the narrative flow and relationships between sentences is critical for analysis. The direct output of sentence embeddings from these models captures the required contextual information effectively.

Furthermore, the same **sentence-transformers** framework can load standard transformer models (e.g., **bert-base-uncased**) that can operate at the token level. When using such base models, the library automatically applies a pooling strategy (typically mean pooling) over the token embeddings to produce a single vector representing the entire input text. This technique effectively creates a token-level embedding for the input text. This approach proved more suitable for the verbal fluency tasks (SFT and PFT) in this study. For these tasks, the primary interest lies in the overall lexical and semantic content of the generated words, rather than the grammatical structure or sequence of individual (often

⁵Sentence Transformers on HuggingFace: <https://huggingface.co/sentence-transformers>

⁶ModernBERT on HuggingFace: <https://huggingface.co/nomic-ai/modernbert-embed-base>

fragmented) utterances. Using a base model via **sentence-transformers** to get a token-level vector captured this global information appropriately.

This dual capability of the **sentence-transformers** library, using both sentence-specialized models for sentence-level tasks and applying pooling to base models for token-level tasks; provides an efficient method for generating task-specific embeddings. It streamlines the process compared to earlier methods that might require manual implementation of pooling strategies or chunk-level processing as demonstrated by [Mirheidari et al. \(2021\)](#).

SpaCy

SpaCy is a powerful NLP library widely used for preprocessing text. It offers tools like tokenization, lemmatization, and stopword removal which help standardize and clean text for analysis. These preprocessing steps ensure the text is consistent and ready for further tasks like feature extraction or integration with models. SpaCy can also extract linguistic features such as part-of-speech tags, syntactic dependencies, and named entities, providing valuable structural insights into the text. Research indicates that embedding-based models frequently outperform those utilizing traditional linguistic features. For example, in the task of native language identification, classifiers trained with Big Bird embeddings significantly surpassed models based on linguistic feature engineering ([Kramp et al., 2023](#)). Similarly, in metaphor identification, combining pre-trained word embeddings like GloVe, ELMo, and BERT with linguistic features led to superior performance compared to using linguistic features alone ([Mao et al., 2021](#)).

SpaCy served as the primary tool for text preprocessing in this study. Applying SpaCy for cleaning and preparation established a consistent data foundation for the experiments, enabling effective analysis by the machine learning models. This preprocessing step is crucial, as model performance often suffers with noisy or inconsistent input. Utilizing SpaCy ensured the data was suitably structured and cleaned for the analysis.

2.6.3 Tools for Model Training and Fine-Tuning

Scikit-Learn

Scikit-Learn is a popular library for implementing traditional machine learning algorithms ([Pedregosa et al., 2011](#)). It offers easy-to-use tools for training and evaluating various traditional machine learning models, including LR and SVM, which are particularly relevant for this project's baseline experiments. Scikit-Learn's simplicity and compatibility with smaller datasets make it an excellent choice for early-stage model development and experimentation.

PyTorch and Hugging Face Transformers

Hugging Face Transformers is a library built on top of PyTorch that provides a powerful framework for fine-tuning pre-trained transformer models such as BERT, and its variants.

These models can be adapted to specific tasks, such as classifying MCI vs. HC, by leveraging domain-specific datasets. While PyTorch serves as the foundation for building and training neural networks, Hugging Face simplifies the process of working with transformers by offering pre-built pipelines and tools for tokenization, training, and evaluation. In this study, Hugging Face Transformers is used for fine-tuning the pre-trained LLMs for the binary classification tasks.

Hyperparameter Optimization with Optuna

Finding the optimal hyperparameters for machine learning models is crucial for achieving peak performance. Hyperparameters, such as learning rates in neural networks or regularization strengths in SVMs, are not learned from the data but must be set before training. Optuna is an open-source hyperparameter optimization framework designed to automate this process efficiently (Akiba et al., 2019).

Optuna employs various optimization algorithms, with the Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) being one of its default and most effective samplers, particularly for complex, conditional search spaces (Bergstra et al., 2011). TPE is a sequential model-based optimization (SMBO) algorithm, a form of Bayesian optimization. Unlike **grid search** or **random search** which explore the hyperparameter space blindly, TPE builds probabilistic models to guide the search towards more promising regions.

Specifically, TPE models $P(x|y)$ and $P(y)$, where x represents hyperparameters and y represents the objective function value (e.g., validation accuracy or loss). It maintains two density estimators: one for hyperparameters associated with good objective values ($l(x)$) and one for those associated with bad objective values ($g(x)$). It then selects the next hyperparameters to evaluate by maximizing the ratio $l(x)/g(x)$, effectively focusing the search on regions likely to yield improvements. This intelligent sampling strategy often finds better hyperparameters in fewer trials compared to traditional methods. Optuna's define-by-run API allows for flexible definition of search spaces, making it suitable for optimizing models developed using frameworks like Scikit-Learn and PyTorch/Hugging Face Transformers.

2.6.4 Data Visualization Tools

Data visualization is crucial for understanding data distributions, feature relationships, and model performance metrics, such as accuracy, precision-recall curves, and confusion matrices. It also helps in identifying class imbalances or data preprocessing requirements.

Matplotlib and Seaborn

Matplotlib is a foundational library for creating static, interactive, and animated visualizations in Python. It can be used to plot feature distributions, such as linguistic or acoustic features, to gain insights into data trends and patterns. Seaborn builds on Matplotlib to provide advanced statistical visualizations. It provides a high-level interface for creating informative and attractive visualizations, such as heatmaps for visualizing

correlations among features or confusion matrices for evaluating model performance.

In conclusion, the tools and libraries discussed in this section form a comprehensive toolkit for researchers working on machine learning tasks. OpenSMILE and linguistic feature extraction tools like SBERT, and SpaCy enable the creation of informative feature sets, while Scikit-Learn, PyTorch, and Hugging Face Transformers facilitate model training and fine-tuning. Data visualization libraries like Matplotlib and Seaborn help in understanding data characteristics and model performance. By leveraging these tools, researchers can develop effective machine learning pipelines for detecting cognitive impairment.

2.7 Existing Research on Automatic Detection

Table 2.2 highlights existing research that has made significant progress in using machine learning to automatically detect cognitive decline from speech. Researchers have analyzed acoustic, linguistic, and other speech features to identify patterns that differentiate between individuals with MCI and HC. A variety of machine learning models have been applied, including SVM, LR, deep learning and ensemble algorithms. The studies vary in dataset size, specific speech tasks analyzed, and types of features extracted.

Table 2.2: Performance Comparison of ML models for MCI vs HC Classification in Related Studies. For cross-lingual studies, only metrics from English-speaking participants are presented.

Study	Dataset (Size)	Model (s)	F1
Gosztolya et al. (2019)	Hungarian Corpus (75)	SVM	0.857
Gosztolya et al. (2021)	Newyork + Szeged Corpus (66)	SVM	0.828
Mirheidari et al. (2023)	CognoSpeak (100)	LR	0.812
Agbavor and Liang (2024)	TAUKADIAL 2024 ⁷ (169)	NN, SVM, LR	0.851
Wang et al. (2025)	TAUKADIAL 2024 (169)	BiLSTM	0.685
Zhang et al. (2025)	PROCESS 2025 ⁸ (157)	RF	0.696

Gosztolya et al. (2019) aimed to distinguish MCI and mild Alzheimer’s disease (mAD) from healthy controls using spontaneous speech. The dataset included 75 participants: 25 with MCI, 25 with mAD, and 25 healthy controls. Acoustic features, such as speech rate and pauses, and linguistic features, like word choice, were extracted from the audio recordings. An SVM classifier was used to analyze the combined features. For the MCI vs HC classification results, the model achieved an F1-score of 85.7% for distinguishing MCI from HC when combining acoustic and linguistic features, and up to 75.6% when using either feature type alone.

⁷TAUKADIAL: The Interspeech 2024 TAUKADIAL Challenge.

⁸PROCESS: Prediction and Recognition Of Cognitive declinE through Spontaneous Speech Challenge 2025.

Gosztolya et al. (2021) aimed to detect MCI from spontaneous speech in a cross-lingual setting. They evaluated speech samples from English- and Hungarian-speaking participants using both English and Hungarian ASR systems to extract acoustic markers such as articulation rate, speech tempo, and hesitation patterns (silent and filled pauses). An SVM classifier was applied to these features. On the test set, for English-speaking subjects with English ASR, the best reported F1-score was 82.8%, and for Hungarian-speaking subjects with Hungarian ASR, it reached 88.9% when using filled pause-related attributes alone

Mirheidari et al. (2023) explored automatic detection using a subset of dataset from the CognoSpeak project (Subsection 3.1.1), comprising 100 participants (50 HC vs 50 MCI). Among the MCI group, 22 participants progressed to prodromal Alzheimer’s disease (pr-AD), while 28 remained non-progressed (non-P). Machine learning models were trained to classify MCI and its subtypes. The classification task was performed using text and acoustic features processed through two ASR systems: KALDI and Wav2Vec2. Wav2Vec2 demonstrated superior performance with reduced word error rates (WER). The best-performing model, which combined text/contextual and acoustic features from Wav2Vec2 outputs, achieved an F1-score of 81.2% for distinguishing MCI from HC. Additionally, when focusing on the more challenging task of distinguishing MCI subtypes, the model attained an F1-score of 75.0% for pr-AD versus non-P and 66.9% for a three-way classification involving pr-AD, non-P, and HC.

Agbavor and Liang (2024) participated in the INTERSPEECH 2024 TAUADIAL Challenge which include both English and Mandarin speakers. The study utilised Whisper, a speech foundation model, to derive embeddings and a language-specific ensemble method combining SVM, LR, and NN. They achieved F1-score of 85.1% (English subset) based on majority voting across three picture description tasks, achieving second place overall in the competition.

Wang et al. (2025) also used the TAUADIAL dataset. They introduced a novel method for MCI detection leveraging W2V-BERT-2.0, a multilingual self-supervised learning model as a frozen feature extractor. They avoided reliance on transcripts by extracting acoustic embeddings directly from speech and used a lightweight BiLSTM classifier enhanced with a custom “OR” inference logic, which predicts MCI if any speech segment indicates impairment. Their model achieved an F1-score of 68.5% on the held-out test set. By introducing a method to identify essential transformer layers and combining features from multiple layers, they improved performance over baselines. The study also revealed challenges such as speaker bias and high sensitivity to data splits, highlighting the need for more robust and generalizable audio features in future MCI detection research.

Zhang et al. (2025) employed Digital Linguistic Biomarkers (DLBs) extracted through a specialized pipeline to detect cognitive decline in the PROCESS 2025 Challenge. The DLB extraction pipeline involved preprocessing audio to transcribe text, detect voice activity, distinguish vowels and consonants, and perform syntactic parsing. Features extracted included acoustic, rhythmic, lexical, syntactic, and Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count (LIWC)-based categories. Their model utilized a two-stage classifier combining a Random

Forest classifier (for distinguishing healthy controls from MCI) and a Multi-Layer Perceptron classifier (for MCI vs dementia). Their method achieved a Macro-F1 score of 69.6%, earning first place in the PROCESS Challenge classification task.

Notably, this research also depends on the PROCESS dataset, and the datasets are analysed in detail in [Chapter 3](#).

2.8 Summary and Research Gaps

Despite promising developments, the literature reviewed reveals persistent methodological issues that may limit the practical application of automatic speech-based screening for MCI. Most current systems rely on training data from small, controlled groups (fewer than 200 participants), often lacking adequate representation of individuals with early-stage cognitive decline. As a result, performance metrics like F1 scores, while strong within individual studies, are highly sensitive to train-test data splits and changes in speaker composition (demographics, language, regional variations, and other factors). For instance, [Wang et al. \(2025\)](#) observed that hidden speaker identity biases caused balanced accuracy to vary by over 12% across cross-validation folds. This highlights the urgent need for larger, diverse, and carefully partitioned datasets. Similarly, the cross-lingual study by [Gosztolya et al. \(2021\)](#) included only 66 speakers per language, restricting the statistical power of their otherwise effective ASR-independent temporal features. [Zhang et al. \(2025\)](#)'s top-performing PROCESS Challenge model achieved a macro-F1 of 69.6% only by initially grouping dementia and MCI into one category, underscoring ongoing difficulties in making fine-grained diagnostic distinctions. Collectively, these findings underscore a critical challenge discussed earlier regarding data scarcity and quality limitations in applying machine learning effectively in healthcare ([Section 2.4.1](#)).

Another important gap is in feature engineering and modelling techniques themselves. Although recent research has shifted towards self-supervised feature extraction methods, many systems still rely heavily on imperfect automatic speech recognition (ASR) transcripts that can degrade with noise or varying conditions. [Mirheidari et al. \(2021\)](#) explicitly highlighted how transcription errors may negatively affect downstream tasks, emphasizing the need to investigate ASR-related errors in the training features.

The literature reviewed guided several choices in this research. Firstly, this study utilizes manually transcribed datasets for linguistic analysis, avoiding reliance on potentially error-prone ASR transcripts. Secondly, to address reported issues of speaker bias and sensitivity to data splits, this research involved extensive dataset analysis and employed bias mitigation techniques, such as stratified cross-validation, to improve model stability. Finally, the use of new and powerful language models remains underexplored in previous studies. Hence, in addition to traditional models, this study also explores BERT and its variants for binary classification tasks. Unlike traditional models, which depend heavily on manually crafted features, fine-tuned LLMs can capture complex linguistic patterns directly from text

data, as highlighted in [Section 2.5](#). By leveraging domain-specific variants of BERT like ClinicalBERT and integrating acoustic and linguistic features, this project aims to overcome the limitations of previous studies, providing a robust and scalable solution for early detection of cognitive decline. Furthermore, it is important to note that the data scarcity issue remains unresolved in this study. Data scarcity continues to be a major challenge in the automatic speech-based detection of MCI.

Chapter 3

Dataset Analysis

This chapter provides a comprehensive analysis of the dataset used in this project, obtained from the CognoSpeak project. Understanding the dataset characteristics is fundamental as it directly informs modelling decisions in the Methodology ([Chapter 4](#)). The chapter begins by describing the data sources including the CognoSpeak project and Prediction and Recognition Of Cognitive declinE through Spontaneous Speech (PROCESS) 2025 corpus ([Section 3.1](#)). It then presents exploratory data analysis covering class distribution, demographic patterns, missing data, and speech characteristics such as filler words and pauses ([Section 3.2](#)). It concludes with a summary of the key findings from this analysis ([Section 3.3](#)).

3.1 Data Sources

This section describes the origins of the dataset used in this study. This context is necessary for understanding the subsequent analyses.

3.1.1 The CognoSpeak Project

The CognoSpeak Project is an innovative ongoing research project that aims to develop an accessible and user-friendly system for remotely assessing people with memory problems. The system uses a virtual agent that interacts with participants through a mobile or web platform. During the assessment, participants interact with one of four avatars representing diverse ethnic and age groups, which helps create a comfortable and relatable experience for users. The virtual agent guides participants through a carefully designed set of questions and tasks developed in collaboration with clinicians and linguists. The assessment covers a wide range of questions and tasks designed to evaluate different aspects of cognitive function. Memory recall is assessed through questions that test both short-term and long-term memory, such as asking about recently noticed memory problems or details about the participant's activities over the last weekend. Cognitive functioning is examined through questions about daily life and personal history, providing insights into the participant's ability to manage everyday tasks and recall biographical information. Furthermore, verbal fluency tests and

picture description tasks, such as those discussed in [Section 2.3](#) are also included in the CognoSpeak assessment.

Throughout the assessment, the CognoSpeak system records audio and, optionally, video data, capturing the participants’ responses and facial expressions. The audio recordings are then automatically transcribed to enable both acoustic and linguistic analysis. The interactions are also manually transcribed to train and refine the automatic speech recognition models. Additionally, CognoSpeak collects various questionnaire-based assessments, such as the MoCA, Multicultural Cognitive Examination, and Rowland Universal Dementia Assessment Scale. However, this project focuses only on verbal fluency and cookie theft data.

3.1.2 PROCESS 2025 Corpus

The PROCESS dataset is a subset of the CognoSpeak project, utilised explicitly in the PROCESS 2025 Challenge. This challenge brought together researchers from academia and industry to develop innovative solutions for early-stage dementia detection through advanced speech signal processing and ML models. The corpus categorises participants into three diagnostic groups: MCI, Dementia, and HC. However, this study focuses exclusively on a binary classification involving the MCI and HC groups.

From the original 197 English-speaking participants (103 HC, 72 MCI, 20 Dementia), Dementia entries were removed, leaving 177 total participants. The dataset had already been pre-divided into training and testing sets, with 141 participants allocated to the training set and 36 participants to the testing set (effectively an 80/20 split). It also includes MMSE scores and demographic metadata for all participants, enabling analysis of cognitive impairment patterns across different demographic groups.

Table 3.1: Demographic Information for the PROCESS Dataset After Removing Dementia Records.

Demographic	HC (n=103)	MCI (n=74)
Age (mean \pm SD)	62.58 \pm 12.92	68.85 \pm 9.82
Gender (male / female)	43 / 59	37 / 37
MMSE score (mean \pm SD)	28.12 \pm 5.04	26.70 \pm 2.32

3.2 Exploratory Data Analysis

This section presents the exploratory data analysis (EDA) performed on the dataset. The analysis identified initial patterns, distributions, and relationships, which informed the subsequent feature engineering and modelling stages. Class balance and demographic distributions across data splits were examined as part of this analysis.

3.2.1 Class Distribution

The dataset has a relatively balanced class distribution, with 58.2% of participants classified as HC and 41.8% as MCI (Figure 3.1a). This near-balanced distribution is advantageous for machine learning, as it reduces the need for complex resampling techniques that might be required for highly imbalanced datasets. Nevertheless, this small difference is considered in the validation strategy for the training pipelines.

(a) Class distribution across diagnostic classes.

(b) Class distribution across train and test splits.

Figure 3.1: Class distribution analysis.

An analysis of the distribution of diagnostic classes across the train and test splits was also conducted to ensure that the model development and evaluation are based on representative data (Figure 3.1b). This analysis is crucial for understanding potential biases that affect model performance. It reveals that both the train and test splits maintain similar class proportions, with the HC class slightly more prevalent in both splits. The train split contains 58.2% HC and 41.8% MCI participants, while the test split has 58.3% HC and 41.7% MCI participants. This relatively consistent distribution is beneficial for model development as it reduces the risk of split-specific biases and helps ensure that the model's performance on the test set will be representative of its real-world performance. Additionally, the small difference in the splits is considered when choosing and interpreting model performance metrics, particularly those sensitive to class distribution.

3.2.2 Demographic Distribution

Age distribution analysis (Figure 3.2a and Figure 3.2b) indicated that HC participants were younger on average (mean 62.6 years) and exhibited more significant variation, while MCI participants were older on average (mean 68.5 years) and had a somewhat narrower age range. These values align with clinical expectations that older individuals face a higher risk of cognitive impairment (National Health Service, 2023).

The gender distribution analysis (Figure 3.3) showed moderate female predominance in the HC group (58.3% female, female-to-male ratio = 1.40) and balanced representation in the MCI group (50% female, ratio = 1.00). Cohen’s d was calculated based on group means and standard deviations, resulting in a small effect size ($d = 0.17$) and confirming minimal demographic differences between groups. Recent studies emphasise the importance of demographic balance, especially gender, to avoid biases in predictive models (Levine et al., 2021; Mielke et al., 2022; Clouston et al., 2024). This fairly balanced gender distribution benefits this study by eliminating the need for extensive demographic resampling during model training.

(a) Age distribution comparison between HC and MCI participants

(b) Box plot showing age distribution statistics for HC and MCI groups.

Figure 3.2: Age distribution analysis.

(a) Gender distribution across diagnostic classes.

(b) Gender distribution across train and test splits.

Figure 3.3: Gender distribution analysis.

3.2.3 Missing-Data Imputation

(a) Percentage of missing Age and MMSE values in the dataset.

(b) Distribution of missing values by diagnostic class.

Figure 3.4: Missing data analysis.

Age and MMSE exhibited notable missingness (Figure 3.4), with 22.0% of age data and 54.2% of MMSE scores absent. Because of the high percentage of missing values for MMSE, it was excluded from further analyses. The risk of bias introduced by attempting to impute such a heavily incomplete feature seemed greater than any potential benefit. For age, a simple mean imputation strategy was adopted using the overall mean age across both HC and MCI groups. Although mean imputation reduces variance and creates artificial peaks at the mean value, it was chosen due to moderate missingness levels and simplicity of implementation. Figure 3.5 shows the effect of the imputation strategy on the age distribution.

The overall mean imputation approach partially obscures the diagnostic class differences between HC and MCI participants that were observed in the original data (HC mean: 62.6 years vs. MCI mean: 68.5 years). This approach was selected to avoid introducing potential bias from class-specific imputation. Despite the imputation, the substantial overlap between age distributions reflects the clinical reality that age alone is not a strong predictor of MCI. Many healthy older adults do not develop cognitive impairment, and some younger individuals can develop MCI. If we were relying on age as a primary feature for classification, this overlap would be problematic. In the context of this research, age is important to include as a potential confounding variable (since speech patterns can change with age), but it's not expected to be the primary discriminative feature.

Figure 3.5: Age distribution before and after imputation, showing the preservation of class differences.

Figure 3.6: Total Filler Word rate by Diagnostic Class (left) and Cognitive Task (right) showing data from a balanced sample of 70 HC and 70 MCI participants. (*ns* = not significant, *p* = *p*-value.)

3.2.4 Disfluencies

Filler Words

Analysis of filler words (e.g., “um,” “er,” “ah”) revealed an unexpected pattern: healthy control participants produced more filler words overall than participants with MCI. The analysis compared filler word usage between 70 healthy controls and 70 participants with

MCI. The HC group produced about 7.66 filler words per 100 words, while the MCI group produced approximately 7.09. Although HC participants consistently used more filler words across tasks (with the Semantic Fluency Task showing the largest numerical difference), the observed difference may not be statistically significant ($p = 0.533$). A p-value represents the probability that an observed difference could have occurred by chance or as a result of random variation. Values below 0.05 suggest the difference is statistically significant, while values above 0.05 suggest the difference may be due to random variation.

Given that the transcripts will be encoded into embeddings for training machine learning models, these findings imply that filler words may not provide a beneficial signal for distinguishing the MCI group — a result that contradicts a previous study that reported increased filler word usage in MCI (Kim et al., 2019). Perhaps this observation proves the hypothesis that MCI is inherently more challenging to detect using speech biomarkers; hence, filler word usage may not be a robust MCI detection biomarker. However, it is too early to draw firm conclusions about the predictive value of filler words for MCI detection. Consequently, our machine learning pipelines were designed to experiment with both retaining and removing filler words when encoding transcript embeddings. This dual approach allows us to assess whether including filler words enhances model performance or simply adds noise, providing valuable insights as further data are collected.

Pauses

Drawing ideas from Yuan et al. (2021), the transcripts were analysed to explicitly find the appropriate buckets to encode speech pauses. The analysis revealed that pauses below 3 seconds were predominant (Figure 3.7) in the HC groups. These shorter pauses are common in everyday speech and mainly represent normal hesitations. A significant overlap was observed between MCI and healthy controls within this range, which further reduced its usefulness for classification. This finding further proves the difficulty of detecting MCI, as its subtle signs make it harder to identify compared to more advanced cognitive impairments such as Alzheimer’s disease. As a result, only two pause groups were chosen: pauses between 3-5 seconds are classified as short, while those longer than 5 seconds are classified as long (see Figure 3.8). Pauses shorter than 3 seconds were removed. This simpler grouping shows a clear difference between the groups, with MCI subjects exhibiting a higher frequency of long pauses compared to healthy controls. These pause markers have been incorporated into the transcripts to support subsequent modelling (Chapter 4).

Figure 3.7: Pause distribution between HC and MCI groups.

Figure 3.8: Frequency distribution of pauses in two categories — short pauses (3–5 seconds) and long pauses (over 5 seconds).

3.3 Key Observations and Summary

The exploratory data analysis revealed several key insights that informed modelling decisions in the Methodology (Chapter 4). The class distribution was nearly balanced (58.2% HC and 41.8% MCI). Small differences between the training and test splits will be handled during model training and evaluation. Demographic analysis indicated that MCI participants were notably older (mean 68.5 vs 62.6 years) with less variance in age distribution. Gender distribution analysis showed a female predominance in HC participants (female-to-male ratio 1.40) compared to perfect gender balance in the MCI group (ratio 1.00).

Challenges with missing data were observed, particularly for MMSE scores (54.2% missing) and age (22.0% missing). Due to the high rate of missing MMSE values, this feature was excluded from further analysis, while age was imputed using overall mean. Analysis of speech patterns in the transcripts revealed two important findings about cognitive markers in speech. Although filler word usage did not show a statistically significant difference between groups, analysis of pause durations revealed that pauses shorter than 3 seconds were common and ineffective for distinguishing HC from MCI. By reclassifying pauses into two categories, pauses between 3 and 5 seconds defined as short and those over 5 seconds as long, a clear distinction emerged, with MCI subjects exhibiting a higher frequency of long pauses. This finding facilitated the inclusion of pause-encoded transcripts into the feature extraction pipelines.

Chapter 4

Methodology

This chapter details the systematic methodology employed to address the research objectives for detecting MCI from speech data, as outlined in [Chapter 1](#). The chapter begins by redefining the specific requirements derived from the four main objectives ([Section 4.1](#)). It then describes the technical infrastructure ([Section 4.2](#)), data preprocessing steps including audio enhancement and transcript standardization ([Section 4.3](#)), and feature engineering strategies for acoustic and linguistic modalities ([Section 4.4](#)), all essential for achieving *Obj. 1*.

The rationale for selecting traditional machine learning models (LR, SVM) and transformer-based approaches (BERT variants) to achieve *Obj. 2* and *Obj. 3* is discussed ([Section 4.5](#)). Subsequently, the comprehensive evaluation framework, prioritizing macro-F1 due to class imbalance and utilizing stratified cross-validation to address *Obj. 4*, is presented ([Section 4.6](#)). Finally, ethical considerations critical for handling medical data are addressed ([Section 4.7](#)). This detailed methodology provides the foundation for the experimental procedures described in [Chapter 5](#).

4.1 Research Objectives (recap) and Requirements

As highlighted in [Chapter 1](#), the primary aim of this project is to develop and evaluate a robust pipeline for MCI detection using speech data. This aim is operationalized through the following four key research objectives:

1. Utilize NLP and audio analysis tools to extract linguistic and acoustic features from transcribed speech data and audio recordings.
2. Train and compare traditional machine learning classifiers (LR and SVMs) using the extracted features.
3. Fine-tune transformer-based Large Language Models (BERT variants) as sequence classifiers for detecting cognitive decline.

4. Assess and compare the performance of the traditional and transformer-based models to identify the most effective classifier for distinguishing between MCI and HC.

To ensure these objectives were met systematically, specific requirements were defined for each. These requirements, categorized by priority (Essential 'E' or Desirable 'D') and their completion status, are consolidated in [Table 4.1](#). Each requirement is assigned a unique identifier (Req. ID) for reference.

Table 4.1: Consolidated Project Requirements by Objective.

Obj.	Req. ID	Requirement Description	Priority	Status
1	R1.1	Clean datasets, remove irrelevant annotations	E	Met
	R1.2	Extract acoustic features (OpenSMILE: ComParE, eGeMAPS)	E	Met
	R1.3	Extract token-level embeddings (SFT, PFT)	E	Met
	R1.4	Extract sentence-level embeddings (CTD)	E	Met
2	R2.1	Train/evaluate SVM and LR classifiers using acoustic features	E	Met
	R2.2	Train/evaluate SVM and LR classifiers using linguistic features	E	Met
	R2.3	Compare SVM/LR performance to select the most robust traditional model	E	Met
3	R3.1	Fine-tune RoBERTa, DistilBERT, and ClinicalBERT for sequence classification	E	Met
	R3.2	Compare performance of fine-tuned LLMs to select the best model	E	Met
4	R4.1	Compare traditional ML models (SVM, LR) with LLMs to identify the most efficient approach	E	Met
	R4.2	Train/evaluate the best-performing classifier using ensemble methods	D	Met

4.2 Toolchain

To ensure reproducibility and clarity of the methodological workflow, [Table 4.2](#) summarizes the primary software libraries and tools used throughout this project.

Table 4.2: Software stack organised by pipeline stage.

Stage	Library / Toolkit	Version	Purpose / Notes
Audio	noisereduce	3.0.3	Audio quality enhancement prior to feature extraction.
	openSMILE	2.5.0	Acoustic feature extraction
Text	spaCy	3.7.2	Tokenisation, sentence segmentation and processing transcripts.
	sentence-transformers	3.4.1	Text embedding extraction.
	Hugging Face Transformers	4.49.0	BERT models fine-tuning for transcript-level classification.
Modelling	scikit-learn	1.6.1	Classical ML (LR, SVM), scaling, cross validation and performance metrics.
	PyTorch	2.2.2	Transformer fine-tuning and inference.
	Optuna	4.2.1	Bayesian hyper-parameter search.
Viz	matplotlib	3.10.1	Distribution plots, ROC curves, confusion matrices.

All data preprocessing and experimental scripts were implemented in Python 3.11.9. The experiments were conducted using the University of Sheffield’s High-Performance Computing (HPC) facilities. Traditional machine learning models were trained using standard CPUs, while transformer models, due to their substantial computational requirements, were trained using a combination of NVIDIA A100 and H100 GPUs.

4.3 Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing is an essential foundation for machine learning models, particularly when working with data that contains inherent variability and noise. Audio recordings often contain background noise, overlapping speech, and inconsistencies that can obscure subtle cognitive markers. Similarly, raw transcripts may include annotations, non-participant speech, and other elements that do not directly reflect the participant’s cognitive state. This preprocessing step addresses these concerns through audio enhancement and transcript standardization techniques, directly supporting the feature extraction requirements outlined in *Obj. 1 (Req. R1.1 - R1.4)*.

4.3.1 Audio Preprocessing

Audio noise reduction was performed using the `noisereducer`¹ Python library, which employs spectral gating techniques to separate speech from background noise. This approach was selected based on its demonstrated effectiveness in preserving speech quality while minimizing artifacts that could affect subsequent feature extraction (Sainburg and Zorea, 2024).

The specific configuration parameters included setting `stationary` to `false`, `prop_decrease` to `0.75`, `n_std_thresh_stationary` to `1.5`, and `time_mask_smooth_ms` to `200` ms. These parameters were optimized through iterative testing to adapt to varying background noise conditions present in the recordings. The non-stationary noise estimation allowed the algorithm to adjust to changing noise profiles throughout each recording. The `prop_decrease` value of `0.75` was selected to apply less aggressive noise reduction, thereby preserving more of the speech signal while still removing sufficient background noise.

Several state-of-the-art speaker diarization techniques were initially evaluated to isolate participant speech segments in the recordings. The primary approaches tested included the PyAnnote framework (using the `pyannote/speaker-diarization-3.1`² model) and NVIDIA’s NeMo diarization toolkit. Despite these advanced techniques representing the current state of the art in speaker separation, preliminary testing revealed that the models frequently misclassified speaker segments, resulting in the unintended removal of participant speech data while retaining other speakers’ segments. Given that participant speech patterns constitute the primary data for subsequent analysis, the decision was made to exclude speaker diarization from the preprocessing pipeline to prevent data loss that could compromise subsequent analysis.

4.3.2 Transcript Preprocessing

The PROCESS transcripts were annotated in CHAT format, containing utterances from participants (marked as “Pat:”) and background speakers (annotated as “Oth:”). The transcripts included timestamps indicating pauses between words and sentences, as well as non-speech interactions (e.g., “(laughs)”, “(coughs)”) enclosed in brackets. Thorough preprocessing of these transcripts was critical for accurate classification. The original CHAT-format transcripts were cleaned by removing annotations that did not correspond to actual participants’ spoken words. Speech segments from other speakers were also excluded to ensure that only the participants’ speech patterns were analyzed.

Pause information was encoded in the transcripts based on effectiveness in AD detection in previous studies (Yuan et al., 2021). For transformer models, where additional information and data patterns can be provided through tokens, pause information was encoded using two special tokens: `<SPS>` for pauses between 3 and 5 seconds and `<LPS>` for pauses longer than 5 seconds. For instance, an original transcript segment: *“The mother is um (3 seconds) washing dishes. I think the sink (2 seconds) is (6 seconds) overflowing”*, would be encoded

¹Noiserduce PyPI: <https://pypi.org/project/noisereducer>

²PyAnnotate Model on HuggingFace: <https://huggingface.co/pyannote/speaker-diarization-3.1>

as:

“ *The mother is um <SPS> washing dishes. I think the sink is <LPS> overflowing.* ”

This encoding was designed to help the models capture temporal patterns in speech that might indicate cognitive decline. For traditional models, which cannot process special tokens directly, pause information was instead represented as numerical features (`long_pause_rate` and `short_pause_rate`).

4.4 Feature Engineering Approach

Multiple feature engineering strategies were used to extract both acoustic and linguistic features to support model development and evaluation (*Obj. 2 and 3*). This section briefly highlights these strategies, key implementation details will be discussed in the relevant pipelines in [Chapter 5](#).

For acoustic features, two standard feature sets (`eGeMAPSv02` and `ComParE2016`) were selected based on their established effectiveness in related studies. The `eGeMAPSv02` set was selected for its computational efficiency and relevance to voice analysis, while the `ComParE2016` set provides a more comprehensive representation of acoustic properties. This is in line with findings from [Huang et al. \(2024\)](#), which highlight the value of individual acoustic features such as pitch, jitter, and MFCCs in cognitive decline detection. These features were extracted using the OpenSMILE toolkit ([Eyben et al., 2010](#)).

For linguistic features, this study combines both transformer embeddings with interpretable task-specific traditional features.

4.5 Model Selection

The selection of appropriate models was guided by their demonstrated efficacy in cognitive decline detection tasks and their ability to process linguistic and acoustic features effectively. This section details the rationale behind the selection of traditional machine learning models and transformer-based approaches, addressing *Obj. 2 and 3*.

For traditional models, LR and Support Vector Machines were selected as primary classifiers due to their consistent performance across related studies ([Gosztolya et al., 2019](#); [Mirheidari et al., 2023](#); [Agbavor and Liang, 2024](#)). These models offer computational efficiency and interpretability, crucial advantages when working with clinical applications where understanding model decisions is essential for clinical validation. Additionally, these models are particularly suitable for the relatively small PROCESS dataset analyzed in this study, as they typically require fewer training examples to achieve stable performance compared to more complex neural architectures.

For large language models, four transformer-based models were selected: BERT and three of its variants - RoBERTa, DistilBERT, and ClinicalBERT. BERT was included as the baseline transformer model that revolutionized NLP tasks with its bidirectional contextual

representations. RoBERTa was chosen for its enhanced training methodology that improves performance over standard BERT. DistilBERT offers a more efficient alternative (Sanh et al., 2019), making it suitable for deployment scenarios with computational constraints. ClinicalBERT was selected for its domain-specific pretraining on medical texts. One could argue that, since ClinicalBERT is tailored for medical texts and our transcripts are mainly conversational, the benefits of its domain-specific pretraining might not fully apply. However, its training on additional clinical data may enhance its ability to detect and analyze language nuances compared to the base BERT model. Moreover, the pause-encoded transcripts could further improve its ability to detect these signals in the speech data. This study would further validate this hypothesis.

4.6 Evaluation Metrics

To address *Obj. 4* (*Req. R4.1* - model assessment and comparison), a comprehensive evaluation framework was established using standard classification metrics. The evaluation approach accounts for the mild class imbalance observed in the dataset (58.2% HC vs. 41.8% MCI), as detailed in [Subsection 3.2.1](#).

4.6.1 Performance Metrics

For binary classification tasks, particularly those with class imbalance, it is essential to consider metrics beyond simple accuracy. The following metrics were used to evaluate model performance:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Positives}} \quad (4.1)$$

Precision quantifies the proportion of predicted positive cases that are actually positive. In clinical contexts, high precision minimizes false alarms when diagnosing MCI.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Negatives}} \quad (4.2)$$

Recall (sensitivity) measures the proportion of actual positive cases correctly identified. High recall ensures that most individuals with cognitive impairment are detected, minimizing missed cases that would benefit from early intervention.

$$\text{F1} = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (4.3)$$

The F1 score provides a balanced measure by taking the harmonic mean of precision and recall, addressing the inherent trade-off between these metrics. This is particularly valuable in clinical applications where both false positives and false negatives have significant consequences.

To account for class imbalance, macro-averaging was applied to these metrics, giving equal weight to both classes regardless of their frequency:

$$\text{Macro-Precision} = \frac{\text{Precision}_{\text{MCI}} + \text{Precision}_{\text{HC}}}{2} \quad (4.4)$$

$$\text{Macro-Recall} = \frac{\text{Recall}_{\text{MCI}} + \text{Recall}_{\text{HC}}}{2} \quad (4.5)$$

$$\text{Macro-F1} = \frac{F1_{\text{MCI}} + F1_{\text{HC}}}{2} \quad (4.6)$$

Macro-F1 was selected as the primary evaluation metric to ensure that model performance on the minority class (MCI) is given equal importance to performance on the majority class (HC). This is critical in clinical applications where missing MCI cases can have significant consequences for patient care.

Additional secondary metrics were included to provide a more comprehensive assessment:

- **Accuracy:** The proportion of correctly classified instances across both classes. While accuracy provides an intuitive overall measure, it can be misleading in the presence of class imbalance, hence its designation as a secondary metric.
- **Specificity:** The proportion of actual negative cases (HC) correctly identified, representing the model’s ability to avoid misclassifying healthy individuals.
- **AUC:** The area under the Receiver Operating Characteristic curve, which evaluates the model’s discriminative ability across different threshold settings, independent of any specific classification threshold.
- **Confusion Matrix:** A detailed breakdown of classification outcomes (true positives, false positives, true negatives, and false negatives), enabling analysis of specific error patterns and informing future improvements.

4.6.2 Cross-Validation Strategy

Stratified 5-fold cross-validation was employed during model training, hyperparameter search, and evaluation due to the mild class imbalance observed in [Chapter 3](#). This approach ensures that each fold maintains the same class distribution as the overall dataset, providing a more reliable assessment of model performance.

4.7 Ethics, Risk Analysis and Summary

When working with medical data, it’s crucial to address ethical considerations such as patient privacy, data security, and potential biases in the model. These aspects have been carefully analyzed as part of the risk assessment for this project (see [Appendix A](#)). The risk register will be updated regularly as the project progresses.

Importantly, ethics approval for the dataset has already been obtained by the CognoSpeak team, so no additional formal application is required for this project. This has been confirmed

by the CognoSpeak team. However, handling the data still requires strict adherence to ethical guidelines. To ensure compliance, data will only be accessed by authorized personnel, and no datasets will be stored in public repositories. Furthermore, once the project is complete, all datasets will be deleted to maintain ethical integrity.

In summary, this chapter established the methodological framework for MCI detection from speech data, addressing the four research objectives. The approach included preprocessing of audio and transcript data, extraction of acoustic and linguistic features, implementation of traditional machine learning models (LR, SVM), and fine-tuning of transformer-based models. Evaluation metrics prioritized macro-F1 to account for class imbalance, with stratified cross-validation ensuring reliable performance assessment. [Chapter 5](#) details the implementation of model training and evaluation pipelines.

Chapter 5

Experimental Setup

This chapter details the implementation of the experimental framework for this study. It builds on the methodological foundations established in [Chapter 4](#), focusing on the technical aspects of implementing and evaluating the modelling pipelines.

The chapter begins by describing the experimental design approach in [Section 5.1](#), including the configuration system that enabled efficient exploration of the complex parameter space. It then provides an overview of the four modelling pipelines investigated in [Section 5.2](#): acoustic machine learning, linguistic machine learning, transformer-based models, and a multimodal ensemble approach. For each pipeline, the implementation details, feature extraction processes, model configurations, and evaluation methodologies are presented. ([Section 5.3](#), [Section 5.4](#), [Section 5.5](#), and [Section 5.6](#))

This chapter provides the technical foundation for understanding the experimental results presented in [Chapter 6](#).

5.1 Experimental Design Approach

The experimental design for this research focused on three key principles: reproducibility, flexibility, and systematic evaluation. This study examined three cognitive tasks (CTD, SFT, and PFT) using various feature extraction methods and model architectures, creating a complex experimental space. Each combination required specific hyperparameter settings, making manual exploration impractical. To address this challenge, a *configuration-driven development* approach was implemented. This approach streamlined experimentation, reduced errors, and allowed for consistent comparison of results across different experimental settings.

5.1.1 Configuration-Driven Development

A modular configuration-based system was developed to separate core implementation code from configurable attributes such as dataset paths, model specifications, hyperparameters, and evaluation settings. All experiments were orchestrated through Python scripts that

loads YAML configuration files (see [Appendix B](#)). These configuration files were structured hierarchically to address different aspects of the experimental pipeline:

- **Data preprocessing configuration files** specify data cleaning and preprocessing parameters for both audio and transcript files.
- **Feature extraction configuration files** define the acoustic and linguistic feature extraction parameters, including which feature sets to use (ComParE or eGeMAPS for acoustic features) and embedding models for linguistic features.
- **Training configuration files** contain model architecture specifications and different hyperparameter optimization strategies explored. They also define training parameters for both traditional classifiers and transformer-based models.
- **Evaluation configuration files** specify evaluation metrics, cross-validation strategies, and results logging preferences.

To ensure configuration integrity, a custom Python package (`ConfigParserV2`¹) was developed to load and validate all configuration files against predefined schemas. This validation process verifies that all required parameters are present and that parameter values fall within acceptable ranges, providing immediate feedback when configuration errors are detected.

5.1.2 Experiment Orchestration

The experimental workflow was designed to support both individual experiments and batch processing of multiple configurations. Results from all experiments were automatically logged in a structured format, capturing not only performance metrics but also the complete configuration used and complete execution time. For computationally intensive operations, particularly transformer model fine-tuning, the system was designed to leverage high-performance computing resources efficiently. Checkpointing mechanisms were implemented to allow for experiment resumption in case of interruptions, and resource utilization was optimized to maximize throughput on the available hardware.

This systematic approach to experimental design offers several key advantages. It ensures reproducibility and reduces cognitive load as experimental settings can be easily modified without code changes. Additionally, the validation system prevents common configuration errors, reducing the likelihood of invalid experimental setups.

¹ConfigParserV2: A custom configuration parser package that loads and verify YAML configuration files. Supports concurrent loading of multiple configuration files and validation against predefined schemas.

5.2 Overview of Modelling Pipelines

The experimental investigation resulted in the development of a multi-level ensemble classification pipeline that integrates multimodal features across cognitive tasks. This approach achieved the highest classification metrics on the CTD task among all explored methodologies (results are discussed in Chapter 6). The ensemble combines acoustic and linguistic modalities through a hierarchical soft voting architecture, capturing both task-specific patterns and cross-task cognitive indicators for improved MCI detection.

Before arriving at this optimal solution, multiple pipeline architectures were explored and evaluated. This chapter details the implementation of four distinct modelling pipelines for MCI detection, each representing a different approach to feature extraction and classification:

Figure 5.1: Multimodal ensemble architecture integrating predictions from multiple feature sets and cognitive tasks through hierarchical soft voting.

- **Pipeline A (Acoustic ML):** Utilizes acoustic features extracted from speech recordings, processed through traditional machine learning algorithms.
- **Pipeline B (Linguistic ML):** Leverages linguistic features derived from transcribed speech, also processed through traditional machine learning algorithms.

- **Pipeline C (Transformer)**: Employs transformer-based language models fine-tuned directly on transcripts, bypassing explicit feature engineering.
- **Pipeline D (Ensemble)**: Integrates predictions from multiple models across different feature modalities and cognitive tasks through a hierarchical voting mechanism, as illustrated in [Figure 5.1](#).

The following sections provide detailed descriptions of each pipeline’s implementation, feature extraction, model configuration, and evaluation methodology. Each pipeline builds on the methodological framework established in [Chapter 4](#).

5.3 Pipeline A (Acoustic ML)

This section details the implementation of the acoustic machine learning pipeline for MCI detection. Each stage of the pipeline is described in detail, with emphasis on the technical implementation.

5.3.1 Acoustic Feature Extraction

Following the audio preprocessing steps outlined in [Subsection 4.3.1](#), acoustic features were extracted from the enhanced audio recordings using the OpenSMILE toolkit (version 2.5.0). Two standardized feature sets were implemented to capture different aspects of speech acoustics, as summarized in [Table 5.1](#).

Table 5.1: Summary of acoustic features extracted for MCI detection.

Feature Set	Features	Description
ComParE2016	6,373	Comprehensive paralinguistic feature set containing spectral, cepstral, prosodic, and voice quality parameters. Includes MFCCs, spectral properties, F0, jitter, shimmer, and HNR with various statistical functionals applied to the low-level descriptors.
eGeMAPSv02	88	Extended Geneva Minimalistic Acoustic Parameter Set designed specifically for voice analysis research. Contains frequency-related parameters (F0, jitter, formants), energy-related parameters (loudness, shimmer), spectral parameters, and temporal features.
Demographic	1	Participant age, used in ablation studies to assess its impact on classification performance. Motivated by the significant age gap between HC and MCI observed in dataset (Subsection 3.2.1).

Both feature sets were extracted at the recording level, producing a single feature vector per participant. Feature standardization was applied using scikit-learn’s StandardScaler to normalize the feature distributions to zero mean and unit variance, ensuring that features with larger scales did not dominate the classification process.

Figure 5.2: Traditional feature extraction pipeline for acoustic and linguistic modalities.

5.3.2 Training and Evaluation

The model training and evaluation process followed a systematic framework to ensure robust performance assessment while maintaining consistency with the original PROCESS challenge structure.

Data Partitioning

The original data split from the PROCESS challenge was maintained (80/20), with 141 examples in the training set and 36 examples in the test set, as detailed in [Subsection 3.2.1](#). This approach ensured consistency with other studies from the challenge using the same dataset ([Zhang et al., 2025](#)) and facilitated direct performance comparisons. The mild class imbalance (58.2% HC vs. 41.8% MCI) was addressed through stratified sampling during cross-validation and appropriate evaluation metrics.

Model Development Process

The model development process consisted of three sequential phases:

1. **Baseline Establishment:** Initial training was performed on the training set using default hyperparameters for both LR and SVM classifiers to establish baseline performance metrics. This step provided a reference point for assessing the impact of subsequent optimizations.

2. **Hyperparameter Optimization:** Hyperparameter search was conducted using Optuna (version 4.2.1), with 100 trials for each classifier-feature set combination. This approach efficiently navigates the hyperparameter space by using the results of previous trials to inform subsequent parameter selections. The optimization was performed exclusively on the training set using 5-fold stratified cross-validation to account for class imbalance. The objective function was defined to maximize macro-F1 score, in line with the evaluation framework established in [Section 4.6](#).
3. **Final Model Training and Evaluation:** Following hyperparameter optimization, final models were trained on the complete training set using the optimal hyperparameter configurations identified through the Bayesian search. These models were then evaluated on the held-out test set to assess generalization performance.

Hyperparameter Search Space

The hyperparameter search spaces were defined comprehensively to explore a wide range of model configurations. [Table 5.2](#) details the parameters and their respective ranges for both Logistic Regression and Support Vector Machine classifiers.

Table 5.2: Hyperparameter search spaces for Logistic Regression and Support Vector Machine classifiers.

Category	Parameter	LR	SVM
Regularization	C penalty	$[10^{-3}, 10^2]$ (log scale) {'l1', 'l2', 'elasticnet', None}	$[10^{-3}, 10^2]$ (log scale) –
Model-specific	solver	{'liblinear', 'lbfgs', 'newton-cg', 'sag', 'saga'}	–
	l1_ratio	[0.0, 1.0]	–
	kernel	–	{'linear', 'poly', 'rbf', 'sigmoid'}
Kernel parameters	gamma	–	$[10^{-5}, 10^{-2}]$ (log scale)
	degree	–	{2, 3, 4, 5}
Training control	max_iter	{100, 200, ..., 1000}	{100, 200, ..., 1000}
	class_weight	{None, 'balanced'}	{None, 'balanced'}
	tol	$[10^{-5}, 10^{-3}]$ (log scale)	$[10^{-5}, 10^{-3}]$ (log scale)

Parameter compatibility constraints were programmatically enforced during optimization to ensure valid model configurations. For LR, solver-penalty compatibility was maintained (e.g., 'liblinear' solver only with 'l1' or 'l2' penalties; 'l1_ratio' only used with 'elasticnet' penalty). For SVM, kernel-specific parameters were only considered when the relevant kernel was selected (e.g., 'degree' only for 'poly' kernel; 'gamma' only for 'rbf', 'poly', and 'sigmoid' kernels). These constraints were implemented using conditional parameter definitions in the Optuna framework.

Model Evaluation

The evaluation metrics described in [Section 4.6](#) were used to comprehensively assess model performance. Particular emphasis was placed on macro-F1 due to the mild class imbalance in the dataset. Additionally, confusion matrices were generated to provide a detailed breakdown of classification outcomes, enabling analysis of specific error patterns.

The performance of models trained on different feature sets (ComParE2016 vs. eGeMAPS) was compared to determine the most effective acoustic representation for MCI detection. Similarly, the performance of different classifiers (LR vs. SVM) was compared to identify the most suitable algorithm for this task. These comparisons provide insights into the trade-offs between model complexity, interpretability, and performance in the context of acoustic-based MCI detection.

5.4 Pipeline B (Linguistic ML)

This section details the implementation of the linguistic machine learning pipeline for MCI detection. The pipeline processes transcribed speech data through text preprocessing, linguistic feature extraction, and machine learning model training and evaluation.

5.4.1 Linguistic Feature Extraction

Building on the transcript preprocessing steps outlined in [Subsection 4.3.2](#), linguistic features were extracted from the standardized transcripts. The feature extraction strategy combined transformer-based embeddings with interpretable task-specific traditional features, as shown in [Figure 5.2](#). [Table 5.3](#) summarizes the extracted features, their dimensions, and descriptions.

Transformer Embeddings

For the CTD task, sentence-level embeddings were generated using the `nommic-ai/modernbert-embed-base` model. Transcripts were segmented into sentences using `spaCy` (version 3.7.2), with each sentence individually embedded. To create a single representation for the entire transcript, the mean vector and standard deviation vector were calculated across all sentence embeddings and concatenated, resulting in a 1,536-dimensional embedding that captures both central tendency and variability of semantic content across the narrative. In contrast, for the verbal fluency tasks, where the analysis centers on the overall lexical content and adherence to task rules rather than sequential narrative structure, a token-level approach was used. The `bert-base-uncased` model was used via the `sentence-transformers` library, which applies mean pooling over token embeddings. The entire list of words produced by the participant was treated as a single document, yielding one 768-dimensional vector representing the overall lexical output.

Table 5.3: Summary of linguistic features extracted for MCI detection.

Feature Type	Dim	Description
Base Features		
Transformer Embeddings	768	Base embedding dimension from transformer models: <code>nomic-ai/modernbert-embed-base</code> for CTD and <code>bert-base-uncased</code> for verbal fluency tasks.
Traditional	6	Task-specific linguistic features capturing various aspects of language production, including lexical diversity, vocabulary/sentence analysis, coherence, and task performance.
Demographic	1	Participant age, used in ablation studies to assess its impact on classification performance.
Combined Features		
CTD	1,543	Sentence-level embeddings vector (1536) + traditional features (total word count, lexical diversity, mean sentence length, filler word ratio, short pause rate, long pause rate) + age.
SFT	775	Token-level embeddings vector (768) + traditional features (valid animal word count, repetitions, intrusions, filler word ratio, short pause rate, long pause rate) + age.
PFT	775	Token-level embeddings vector (768) + traditional features (valid 'p' word count, repetitions, rule-breaking errors, filler word ratio, short pause rate, long pause rate) + age.

Traditional Features

Task-specific linguistic features were extracted using a custom Python feature extraction pipeline developed with `spaCy`. For CTD, the full set of **six features** included: total word count, lexical diversity (type-token ratio), mean sentence length, filler word ratio, short pause rate, and long pause rate. Total word count measured language production volume. Lexical diversity assessed vocabulary richness. Mean sentence length indicated grammatical complexity. Filler word ratio measured speech disfluencies.

For SFT, the six features were: valid word count (animals), total repetitions, intrusions (non-animal words), filler word ratio, short pause rate, and long pause rate. Valid words measured semantic retrieval success. Repetitions indicated potential monitoring issues. Intrusions suggested difficulty maintaining semantic boundaries.

Similarly, for PFT, the six features were: valid word count (words starting with “p”), total repetitions, rule-breaking errors (words not starting with “p”), filler word ratio, short pause rate, and long pause rate. Rule-breaking errors highlighted difficulties with task constraints and executive control.

Combined Features

The final feature vectors integrated the transformer embeddings, traditional features, and demographic information (age) to create comprehensive representations for each task. Feature standardization was applied using scikit-learn’s StandardScaler to normalize the feature distributions, ensuring that features with larger scales did not dominate the classification process.

5.4.2 Training and Evaluation

The model training and evaluation process for the linguistic pipeline followed the same systematic framework in pipeline A (Subsection 5.3.2). This ensured consistency in the evaluation methodology across different feature types and facilitated direct comparisons between acoustic and linguistic models.

5.5 Pipeline C (Transformer)

This section details the implementation of the transformer-based pipeline for MCI detection. Unlike the traditional machine learning approaches in Pipelines A and B, this pipeline leverages the contextual understanding capabilities of transformer models to directly classify transcripts.

5.5.1 Transcript Preprocessing

The transformer pipeline utilized pause-encoded transcripts prepared according to preprocessing steps described in the Methodology (Subsection 4.3.2). During implementation, special tokens (<SPS> and <LPS>) were added to each model’s tokenizer vocabulary, ensuring they were treated as distinct semantic units rather than being split into subword tokens.

Additional preprocessing formatted the transcripts to meet transformer model input requirements. For the Cookie Theft task, sentence boundaries were marked with [SEP] tokens to mirror BERT’s pre-training structure:

“ [CLS] *The lady is washing dishes.* [SEP] *The sink is overflowing.* [SEP] *The boy is reaching for cookies.* [SEP] ”

For verbal fluency tasks, all elicited words were concatenated with a single [SEP] token at the end to preserve potential lexical associations:

“ [CLS] *cats dogs elephants kangaroos apples bananas grapes oranges* [SEP] ”

By default, HuggingFace’s tokenizer automatically adds special tokens, but given the different segmentation strategies required for the tasks in this study, this was explicitly disabled (`add_special_tokens=False`). This manual approach simplified the fine-tuning implementation and ensured that tokens were consistently and accurately placed, respecting task-specific formatting requirements.

5.5.2 Fine-tuning and Evaluation

The model training and evaluation process for the transformer pipeline extends the same systematic framework established in Pipeline A (Subsection 5.3.2) — *baseline, hyperparameter optimization, training, and evaluation*. Several transformer-specific adaptations were implemented to address the unique challenges of fine-tuning large language models on a limited dataset.

First, each transformer model was fine-tuned separately for the three cognitive tasks to account for their distinct linguistic characteristics. Maximum sequence length was set to 512 tokens for Cookie Theft (usually containing longer narrative responses) and 256 tokens for verbal fluency tasks (with shorter list-like responses).

Second, a weighted cross-entropy loss function addressed the class imbalance (58.2% HC, 41.8% MCI). Class weights were calculated using:

$$w_c = \frac{N}{K \cdot N_c} \quad (5.1)$$

where N is the total training examples (141), K is the number of classes (2), and N_c is the count of examples in class c . This yielded weights of **0.86** for HC and **1.20** for MCI.

Finally, to account for the high variance often observed when fine-tuning transformer models on small datasets, a robust evaluation approach was implemented. Ten independent fine-tuning runs were performed with different random seeds, with early stopping to minimize overfitting, and the best model from each run was evaluated on the untouched test set. Performance metrics were reported as mean \pm standard deviation across the 10 runs, providing a more reliable estimate of model performance than a single run.

Hyperparameter Search Space

Table 5.4 details the Optuna hyperparameter search spaces for the transformer models. Key focus was placed on parameters that directly impact model performance and training stability.

Table 5.4: Hyperparameter search spaces for transformer models.

Category	Parameter	Search Range
Optimization	Learning Rate	$[1e - 05, 1e - 04]$ (log scale)
	Weight Decay	$[0.0, 0.1]$ (low, high)
	Warmup Ratio	$[0.0, 0.1]$ (low, high)
Training Control	Epochs	$\{2, 3, \dots, 20\}$
	Batch Size	$\{4, 8, 16\}$

5.6 Pipeline D (Ensemble)

This section presents the optimal multilevel ensemble approach for MCI detection (illustrated in Figure 5.1). Comparative analysis of the previous pipelines revealed that Logistic Regression models consistently outperformed other classifiers on this task (results detailed in Chapter 6). Building on this finding, the ensemble pipeline combines predictions from multiple Logistic Regression classifiers, one for each combination of cognitive task (CTD, SFT, PFT) and feature set (linguistic, ComParE, eGeMAPS), to improve classification accuracy and robustness.

5.6.1 Multi-level Ensemble Architecture

Nine Logistic-Regression models are fitted on their respective train splits only. Within each cognitive task, the three trained models are wrapped in a scikit-learn `VotingClassifier` configured for soft voting. Because `VotingClassifier` does not learn extra parameters beyond the averaging rule, its fitting step uses the same train data and adds no new information.

For evaluation, the test splits, which remain untouched during training, are passed once through the trained pipelines:

- **Feature-level stage:** Each task’s `VotingClassifier` produces a probability by averaging the three feature-specific posteriors, yielding CTD_{SOFT3} , SFT_{SOFT3} , and PFT_{SOFT3} .
- **Task-level stage:** The three task-level probabilities are averaged to obtain a single global posterior (ALL_{SOFT9}), which is thresholded at 0.5 to give the final predicted class.

This hierarchical approach integrates complementary information across modalities and tasks to improve classification results.

In summary, this chapter established a comprehensive experimental framework for MCI detection. The configuration-driven approach enabled efficient parameter space exploration and ensured experimental reproducibility. Key technical contributions include standardized feature extraction pipelines, robust hyperparameter optimization strategies, and a novel hierarchical ensemble architecture that leverages complementary information across modalities and tasks. Chapter 6 examines the performance outcomes of these implementations.

Chapter 6

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the experimental results and analysis of the MCI detection pipelines developed in this study. It evaluates the performance of acoustic, linguistic, transformer-based, and ensemble approaches across multiple cognitive tasks.

The chapter begins with an overview of the evaluation methodology in [Section 6.1](#), followed by detailed performance analysis of each pipeline in [Section 6.2](#). A series of ablation studies in [Section 6.3](#) investigates the impact of key components including audio preprocessing, age as a covariate, pause encoding, and feature combinations. Error patterns are examined in [Section 6.4](#), providing insights into model behavior across different classification thresholds. The chapter concludes with a comparison to prior work in [Section 6.5](#) and a summary of key findings in [Section 6.6](#).

6.1 Evaluation Approach

As highlighted in the methodology, this study reports multiple metrics: **macro-precision**, **macro-recall**, **macro-F1**, **specificity** (recall of the HC class), **accuracy**, and **ROC-AUC**. Due to the mild class imbalance in the dataset, **macro-F1** was prioritized as the primary evaluation metric. For transformer models, results represent the mean and standard deviation across 10 independent runs with different random seeds to account for variability. The original PROCESS challenge train/test split was maintained for all experiments to ensure direct comparability with similar studies using the same dataset.

6.2 Pipeline Results

This section presents performance results for each pipeline. It compares their performance across the three cognitive tasks and highlights the strengths and limitations of each approach.

6.2.1 Pipeline A: Acoustic ML Models

The Logistic Regression model using the ComParE features on the CTD task achieved the best acoustic performance (macro-F1: 0.886), as shown in Table 6.1. This result surpasses all other acoustic configurations tested, highlighting that longer, spontaneous speech samples provide richer acoustic markers of cognitive impairment than shorter fluency tasks.

Table 6.1: Performance comparison of acoustic machine learning models across cognitive tasks.

Features	Task	Model	Acc.	Macro-Prec.	Macro-Rec.	Macro-F1	Spec.	AUC
ComParE	CTD	LR	0.889	0.886	0.886	0.886*	0.905	0.854
		SVM	0.833	0.836	0.819	0.825	0.905	0.895
	SFT	LR	0.750	0.750	0.729	0.733	0.857	0.708
		SVM	0.694	0.685	0.681	0.682	0.762	0.689
	PFT	LR	0.778	0.771	0.771	0.771	0.810	0.832
		SVM	0.694	0.688	0.691	0.688	0.714	0.794
eGeMAPS	CTD	LR	0.861	0.861	0.871	0.860	0.810	0.940
		SVM	0.778	0.776	0.762	0.766	0.857	0.867
	SFT	LR	0.667	0.657	0.657	0.657	0.714	0.695
		SVM	0.806	0.813	0.786	0.793	0.905	0.857
	PFT	LR	0.694	0.685	0.681	0.682	0.762	0.627
		SVM	0.639	0.688	0.576	0.535	0.952	0.779

Figure 6.1: Comparison of macro-F1 scores between LR and SVM models across the three cognitive tasks using ComParE features. LR consistently outperforms SVM across tasks.

Logistic regression consistently outperformed the support vector machines in all six configurations using ComParE features (Figure 6.1). With only 141 training samples, logistic regression’s simplicity and regularization effectively handle the highly correlated ComParE feature vectors. A similar pattern can also be observed in the eGeMAPS configurations, except for the phonemic fluency task, where SVM outperforms LR.

Overall, the Cookie-Theft task elicits complex, sustained speech affected by cognitive impairment, which is easily captured acoustically. Conversely, fluency tasks involve brief utterances that limit the ability to detect prosodic differences. High specificity across models (0.81–0.95) indicates healthy controls were rarely misclassified; however, lower sensitivity can be seen on fluency tasks (lowest (0.576) missing nearly half of the MCI cases) indicates a gap best addressed by integrating linguistic analysis.

6.2.2 Pipeline B: Linguistic ML Models

Table 6.2 presents the performance metrics for LR and SVM classifiers trained on the combined linguistic features across all three cognitive tasks.

Table 6.2: Performance comparison of linguistic machine learning models across cognitive tasks.

Task	Model	Acc.	Macro-Prec.	Macro-Rec.	Macro-F1	Spec.	AUC
CTD	LR	0.833	0.855	0.810	0.819*	0.952	0.733
	SVM	0.667	0.658	0.638	0.639	0.810	0.702
SFT	LR	0.750	0.765	0.719	0.724	0.905	0.718
	SVM	0.667	0.685	0.619	0.607	0.905	0.657
PFT	LR	0.583	0.575	0.576	0.575	0.619	0.603
	SVM	0.639	0.650	0.586	0.563	0.905	0.629

Linguistic models achieved the highest macro-F1 score of 0.819 (using the logistic regression model), failing to match acoustic results on any task. Despite this, linguistic features follow a similar task-dependent pattern, with CTD yielding the best performance. The LR model substantially outperformed SVM on the CTD task, a consistent pattern with the acoustic models.

Performance decreases noticeably across tasks, with SFT showing moderate classification power and PFT performing poorly (macro-F1: 0.575). This contradicts the expectation that linguistic features would improve PFT classification. Earlier analysis of acoustic models revealed poor sensitivity (recall) on PFT tasks, particularly with SVM using eGeMAPS. However, linguistic features fail to address this gap effectively, suggesting that phonemic fluency presents inherent challenges for both acoustic and linguistic analysis.

6.2.3 Pipeline C: Transformer Models

Table 6.3 presents the performance metrics for the four transformer models across the cognitive tasks. Accuracy is omitted from the table due to space constraints. Additionally,

transformer models yielded different results each run with different random seeds, hence each metric represents the mean \pm standard deviation across 10 independent fine-tuning runs.

Table 6.3: Performance comparison of transformer models across cognitive tasks. ClinicalBERT achieved the best overall performance on semantic fluency task (macro-F1: 0.693). Values represent mean \pm standard deviation across 10 runs.

Task	Model	Macro-Prec.	Macro-Rec.	Macro-F1	Spec.	AUC
CTD	BERT	0.658 \pm 0.024	0.624 \pm 0.025	0.616 \pm 0.029	0.806 \pm 0.042	0.625 \pm 0.029
	RoBERTa	0.552 \pm 0.077	0.582 \pm 0.032	0.540 \pm 0.055	0.863 \pm 0.050	0.626 \pm 0.028
	DistilBERT	0.655 \pm 0.023	0.633 \pm 0.022	0.626 \pm 0.024	0.746 \pm 0.039	0.632 \pm 0.034
	ClinicalBERT	0.627 \pm 0.029	0.616 \pm 0.020	0.607 \pm 0.021	0.713 \pm 0.059	0.614 \pm 0.022
SFT	BERT	0.706 \pm 0.026	0.672 \pm 0.026	0.668 \pm 0.029	0.810 \pm 0.034	0.699 \pm 0.023
	RoBERTa	0.674 \pm 0.065	0.660 \pm 0.030	0.645 \pm 0.051	0.812 \pm 0.048	0.687 \pm 0.029
	DistilBERT	0.705 \pm 0.022	0.681 \pm 0.019	0.678 \pm 0.019	0.806 \pm 0.062	0.703 \pm 0.024
	ClinicalBERT	0.716 \pm 0.022	0.694 \pm 0.017	0.693 \pm 0.019*	0.801 \pm 0.050	0.721 \pm 0.028
PFT	BERT	0.654 \pm 0.027	0.635 \pm 0.018	0.631 \pm 0.018	0.763 \pm 0.052	0.639 \pm 0.022
	RoBERTa	0.664 \pm 0.040	0.638 \pm 0.022	0.624 \pm 0.030	0.822 \pm 0.050	0.662 \pm 0.018
	DistilBERT	0.687 \pm 0.019	0.658 \pm 0.024	0.654 \pm 0.026	0.779 \pm 0.059	0.662 \pm 0.026
	ClinicalBERT	0.674 \pm 0.022	0.658 \pm 0.016	0.654 \pm 0.018	0.735 \pm 0.077	0.670 \pm 0.021

Transformer models showed surprisingly lower performance than traditional machine learning models. ClinicalBERT achieved the highest macro-F1 score of 0.693, suggesting that domain-specific pre-training did improve performance. Unlike traditional models where CTD task consistently yielded the highest macro-F1 scores, transformers performed best on the semantic fluency task.

The success of transformers on the semantic-fluency task may be tied to several factors. First, transformers fine-tune more easily on these compact sequences because input length stays within the 512-token window, avoiding truncation that harms the Cookie-Theft transcripts. Second, fluency scoring hinges on semantic similarity e.g. animals, fruits, and so on. The masked-language pre-training objective teaches models to predict semantically related words, so transformers excel when the task rewards that lexical association. Finally, perhaps the most critical is the data limitation. 141 examples is not enough for transformers to capture patterns necessary for MCI detection. Moreover, results varied minimally (within ± 0.05), showing models were stable but data-constrained.

Overall, the discrepancy between transformer and traditional ML results highlights how these approaches capture different linguistic characteristics of cognitive impairment. Transformers performed best on semantic fluency tasks, leveraging their strengths in modeling semantic associations. Conversely, traditional ML models excelled at the Cookie Theft Description task by effectively capturing detailed acoustic and linguistic features from structured speech. This complementary performance suggests that future research should explore ensemble methods combining transformers and traditional ML models, potentially capturing a more comprehensive representation of cognitive impairment patterns.

6.2.4 Pipeline D: Ensemble Models

The multimodal hierarchical ensemble results shown in Table 6.4 demonstrate remarkable performance improvements over individual pipelines.

Table 6.4: Performance comparison of hierarchical ensemble models showing results at both feature-level and task-level voting stages. The CTD task ensemble achieves the highest performance (F1: 0.933), while the task-level ensemble demonstrates strong overall performance by integrating predictions from all cognitive tasks.

Level	Ensemble	Acc.	Prec.	Rec.	F1	Spec.	AUC
Feature-level	CTD _{SOFT3}	0.944	0.933	0.933*	0.933	0.943	0.975
	SFT _{SOFT3}	0.750	0.750	0.600	0.667	0.729	0.775
	PFT _{SOFT3}	0.639	0.562	0.600	0.581	0.633	0.756
Task-level	ALL _{SOFT9}	0.889	0.923	0.800	0.857	0.876	0.908

The CTD_{SOFT3} feature-level ensemble achieved a macro-F1 score of 0.933, significantly outperforming the best individual models: *acoustic* (0.886), *linguistic* (0.819), and *transformer* (0.693). This substantial improvement suggests that acoustic and linguistic features capture complementary aspects of cognitive impairment in narrative speech, which aligns with findings by (Gosztolya et al., 2019).

Performance varies considerably across tasks, following the same pattern observed in individual pipelines. The CTD task yields the strongest ensemble results, while SFT and PFT ensembles achieve lower performance metrics (macro-F1 of 0.667 and 0.639 respectively). The consistent superiority of CTD across all pipelines is further demonstrated by the task-level ensemble (ALL_{SOFT9}), which achieves a macro-F1 score of 0.857. While this is slightly lower than the CTD-specific ensemble, it maintains strong performance with higher robustness by integrating predictions from all three cognitive tasks. Moreover, it is a significant improvement considering the lower scores in both SFT and PFT ensembles.

These results validate the hierarchical ensemble approach as a powerful framework for MCI detection, effectively leveraging the strengths of multiple modalities and cognitive tasks. The substantial improvement over individual pipelines demonstrates that no single approach can capture all aspects of cognitive impairment, highlighting the value of integrated multimodal analysis.

6.3 Ablation Studies

This section examines the impact of specific design choices on model performance through controlled experiments. Each study isolates a single variable to measure its contribution in the classification pipelines.

6.3.1 Impact of Audio Processing on Acoustic Pipeline

Table 6.5 presents the impact of audio processing step (specifically noise reduction) on the performance of the best acoustic models ($LR_{ComParE}$ and $LR_{eGeMAPS}$).

Table 6.5: Impact of audio preprocessing on the acoustic model performance (macro-F1) for the CTD task.

Model	With Processing	Without Processing	Difference
$LR_{ComParE}$	0.886	0.858	-0.028
$LR_{eGeMAPS}$	0.860	0.798	-0.062

The results show that audio preprocessing step improved the acoustic models. Both feature sets performed better after noise reduction. While both feature sets benefit from preprocessing, eGeMAPS features show a more pronounced improvement (7.8% increase in macro-F1) compared to ComParE features (3.3% increase). This makes sense because eGeMAPS focuses on voice-quality features (e.g., jitter, shimmer, Harmonics-to-noise ratio (HNR)) that are more affected by noise. These results underscore the importance of audio noise reduction in speech-based MCI detection pipelines.

6.3.2 Impact of Age as a Covariate

Age was added as covariate in the traditional machine learning pipelines following the dataset analysis. This ablation study examines it affects model performance by comparing classification results with and without age as an input feature. Table 6.6 shows the results, focusing on the best-performing models from each pipeline.

Table 6.6: Impact of age as a covariate on classification performance.

Pipeline	Model	With Age	Without Age	Difference
Acoustic	$LR_{ComParE}$	0.886	0.858	-0.028
Linguistic	LR_{Text}	0.819	0.819	0.000
Ensemble	CTD_{SOFT3}	0.933	0.857	-0.076

Adding age improved performance for acoustic and ensemble models but not for the linguistic model. This suggests linguistic features in this dataset already capture cognitive differences clearly, and age provides no extra information. However, it doesn't mean linguistic markers are completely unrelated to age. Age-related linguistic changes are subtle in MCI, while vocal changes are usually more obvious - even in healthy older adults.

6.3.3 Impact of Pause Encoding

As highlighted in the methodology (Subsection 4.3.2), short and long pauses were encoded in the transcripts using two special tokens (<SPS> and <LPS>). Table 6.7 and Figure 6.2 illustrate how these tokens influenced performance in the transformer pipeline.

Table 6.7: Impact of pause encoding on classification performance on the semantic fluency task.

Model	With Pause Tokens	Without Pause Tokens	Difference
BERT	0.668 ± 0.029	0.620 ± 0.025	-0.048
RoBERTa	0.645 ± 0.051	0.586 ± 0.034	-0.059
DistilBERT	0.678 ± 0.019	0.643 ± 0.016	-0.035
ClinicalBERT	0.693 ± 0.019	0.653 ± 0.011	-0.040

Figure 6.2: Comparison of transformer model performance (macro-F1) with and without pause token encoding on the semantic fluency task.

Pause encoding improved performance across all transformer models. RoBERTa improved the most (+0.059 macro-F1), followed by BERT (+0.048), ClinicalBERT (+0.040), and DistilBERT (+0.035). The consistent improvement across models show that hesitation patterns captured by the custom special tokens carried sufficient diagnostic information that helps the transformers separate MCI from healthy controls on the semantic-fluency task.

6.3.4 Feature Set Comparison

Different combinations of features were evaluated to measure their contribution to classification performance before choosing the final ensemble. Table 6.8 summarizes these comparisons, highlighting how each combination affects model performance.

The analysis of feature pairings in the CTD task reveals that while individual acoustic and linguistic models perform well, their combinations yield mixed results. Notably, the *ComParE + Linguistic* pairing underperforms (0.640 macro-F1), suggesting potential feature interference or overfitting. This may be due to overlapping information between the two modalities or challenges in effectively integrating diverse feature types. However, the full

Table 6.8: Performance comparison of feature set combinations on the CTD task.

Feature Combination	Macro-F1	Specificity	AUC	Relative to Best
Individual Features				
ComParE only	0.886	0.905	0.854	-0.047
eGeMAPS only	0.860	0.810	0.832	-0.073
Linguistic only	0.819	0.952	0.733	-0.114
Ensemble (Soft Voting)				
ComParE + eGeMAPS	0.867	0.886	0.975	-0.066
ComParE + Linguistic	0.640	0.719	0.924	-0.293
eGeMAPS + Linguistic	0.769	0.571	0.483	-0.164
All Features (CTD _{SOFT3})	0.933	0.943	0.975	0.000

ensemble combining all three feature sets (ComParE, eGeMAPS, and Linguistic) achieves the highest performance (0.933 macro-F1), indicating that, when properly integrated, these modalities provide complementary information beneficial for MCI detection.

6.4 Error Analysis

This section analyzes error patterns of the multi-level ensemble architecture.

Figure 6.3: Confusion matrices for the task-specific ensemble (CTD_{SOFT3} , left) and the task-level ensemble (ALL_{SOFT9} , right).

The confusion matrices in Figure 6.3 reveal distinct error patterns in the ensemble models. The best performing CTD_{SOFT3} ensemble correctly classified 34 out of 36 test examples (94.4% accuracy), with only one false negative and one false positive. In contrast, the ALL_{SOFT9} task-level ensemble achieves 88.9% accuracy but shows an asymmetric error pattern. While maintaining high specificity (95.2%), sensitivity drops to 80.0% with three false negatives. This bias occurs because the weaker fluency tasks contribute equally to the final decision despite providing less discriminative power in individual models. Perhaps, a weighted ensemble could have improved performance.

The ROC analysis in Figure 6.4 provides additional insights into model behavior across different classification thresholds. The CTD_{SOFT3} ensemble demonstrates superior discrimination (AUC: 0.975) compared to fluency task ensembles (SFT: 0.775, PFT: 0.756). The steeper curve for CTD indicates higher-confidence decisions, while the gradual curves for fluency tasks suggest greater uncertainty.

The ALL_{SOFT9} ensemble (AUC: 0.908) shows an interesting pattern. At high-specificity thresholds, it underperforms compared to CTD_{SOFT3} , but when prioritizing sensitivity, it initially outperformed the CTD_{SOFT3} model before eventually falling behind. This suggests task combination particularly benefits sensitivity-focused screening applications.

These error patterns indicate that optimal clinical deployment requires threshold calibration based on screening objectives, i.e., adjusting the classification threshold to prioritize either sensitivity or specificity depending on the clinical context. The CTD_{SOFT3} ensemble offers the most balanced error profile for general screening, while the task-level ensemble provides valuable redundancy for robustness in real-world applications. The

Figure 6.4: ROC curves for ensemble models across three cognitive tasks and the combined task-level ensemble.

consistent pattern of false negatives observed in the confusion matrices, particularly for MCI further confirms the difficulty of detecting MCI, even with sophisticated model architectures.

6.5 Comparison with prior work

This section highlights performance comparisons with recent research in speech-based MCI detection. It should be noted that this is not a completely fair comparison, as some of these studies used different datasets and cognitive tasks. Additionally, several studies that employed other evaluation metrics were also excluded. Nevertheless, this comparison still provides a relatively rough benchmark for assessing how well our models are performing.

The hierarchical ensemble approach developed in this study significantly outperforms recent research. The CTD_{SOFT3} which achieved a macro-F1 score of 0.933 is a substantial improvement over the results reported by [Zhang et al. \(2025\)](#) (F1: 0.696) on the same PROCESS dataset. The task-level ensemble (ALL_{SOFT9}) with an F1 score of 0.857 also outperforms [Zhang et al. \(2025\)](#) while providing the additional advantage of integrating information across multiple cognitive tasks. This approach aligns with [Agbavor and Liang \(2024\)](#), who achieved an F1 score of 0.851 using majority voting across three picture description tasks.

Table 6.9: Comparison of the current study’s results with recent prior work in speech-based MCI detection.

Study	Dataset (Size)	Features	Model	F1
Agbavor and Liang (2024)	TAUKADIAL (169)	Acoustic (Whisper)	NN, SVM, LR	0.851
Wang et al. (2025)	TAUKADIAL (169)	Acoustic (W2V-BERT-2.0)	Bi-LSTM	0.685
Zhang et al. (2025)	PROCESS (157)	Acoustic + Linguistic DLBs	RF	0.696
Current Study	PROCESS (157)	Acoustic + Linguistic	LR (CTD _{SOFT3})	0.933
Current Study	PROCESS (157)	Acoustic + Linguistic	LR (ALL _{SOFT9})	0.857
Current Study	PROCESS (157)	Linguistic	ClinicalBERT	0.693

Transformer-based ClinicalBERT model trained on transcripts yields 0.693 macro-F1, narrowly beating Wang et al. (2025)’s purely acoustic Bi-LSTM model (macro-F1: 0.685). However, the model architectures are not directly comparable, ClinicalBERT is a 12-layer bidirectional Transformer whose entire stack is fine-tuned, whereas Wang et al. (2025)’s uses a five-layer stacked light-weight Bi-LSTM model.

Nevertheless, the superior performance of the ensemble approach addresses several limitations identified in prior work. Unlike Zhang et al. (2025), who initially grouped dementia and MCI into one category due to difficulties in making fine-grained diagnostic distinctions, the current study successfully distinguishes between MCI and HC with high accuracy.

6.6 Summary

This chapter evaluated multiple approaches for detecting MCI from speech, resulting in a hierarchical ensemble architecture that significantly outperforms prior work. Key findings include:

The CTD task consistently yielded the strongest classification performance across all pipelines, with the CTD_{SOFT3} ensemble achieving a macro-F1 score of 0.933. This confirms that longer, spontaneous narrative speech provides richer diagnostic information than shorter fluency tasks. Acoustic features, particularly the ComParE feature set, demonstrated strong discriminative power (macro-F1: 0.886), outperforming both linguistic features (macro-F1: 0.819) and transformer models (macro-F1: 0.693). Transformer-based models showed task-dependent performance patterns that differed from traditional machine learning approaches. While traditional models performed best on the CTD task, transformers achieved their highest performance on semantic fluency with ClinicalBERT model. This suggests that transformers’ contextual understanding benefits tasks involving semantic relationships, though their overall performance was limited by the dataset size.

Ablation studies revealed several important insights: (1) *audio preprocessing improved acoustic model performance by up to 7.8%*, (2) *age as a covariate enhanced acoustic and ensemble models but not linguistic models*, and (3) *pause encoding consistently improved transformer performance across all models, confirming the diagnostic value of hesitation patterns*.

The hierarchical ensemble approach effectively leveraged complementary information from multiple modalities, with the full ensemble achieving a 5.3% improvement over the best individual model. The task-level ensemble ($\text{ALL}_{\text{SOFT9}}$) demonstrated robust performance (macro-F1: 0.857) by integrating predictions across cognitive tasks, offering valuable redundancy for real-world applications. Comparison with prior work confirmed the superiority of this approach, with the $\text{CTD}_{\text{SOFT3}}$ ensemble outperforming recent studies on the same PROCESS dataset by a substantial margin (23.7% improvement over [Zhang et al. \(2025\)](#)).

Chapter 7

Conclusions and Future Work

This dissertation investigated the development of a robust machine-learning pipeline for detecting MCI using speech data. The research was motivated by the critical need for non-invasive, accessible, and cost-effective methods for early detection of cognitive decline, which could significantly improve intervention outcomes and quality of life for affected individuals. Traditional clinical methods for MCI detection are often resource-intensive, expensive, and not widely accessible, highlighting the need for alternative approaches. This study implemented and systematically evaluated four distinct modelling pipelines using speech recordings of three cognitive tasks (Cookie Theft Description, Semantic Fluency, and Phonemic Fluency) from the PROCESS 2025 Challenge.

Key achievements include the development of a robust multi-level ensemble pipeline that leverages both acoustic and linguistic features through a logistic regression model. This approach achieved state-of-the-art performance with a macro-F1 score of 0.933 and AUC of 0.975 on the Cookie Theft task, a significant improvement over the best results reported by similar studies using the same dataset. Additionally, the transformer-based pipeline demonstrated that domain-specific ClinicalBERT improves classification accuracy, offering a novel perspective previously unexplored in similar studies. Ablation studies provided practical insights into technique impacts on model performance, highlighting improvements of up to 7.8% from audio preprocessing and confirming the efficacy of pause encoding in transformer-based models.

Despite these achievements, several limitations must be acknowledged. The relatively small dataset constrained performance, particularly for transformer models. The research exclusively utilized linguistic inputs for transformer architectures, omitting direct transformer-based acoustic analysis. Emerging transformer models such as Whisper, capable of direct acoustic analysis, were not explored and represent a promising avenue for future work. Additionally, the study's focus on English-speaking participants limits generalizability, and crucial demographic factors such as education level, socioeconomic status, and cultural background were insufficiently addressed due to data constraints. Speaker-identity bias was also not explicitly evaluated despite prior research indicating its significant potential impact [Wang et al. \(2025\)](#).

Future research should prioritize collecting larger and more diverse datasets to improve the generalizability and robustness of transformer-based approaches. Exploring speaker-identity bias mitigation strategies, including data augmentation and robust feature selection less sensitive to speaker traits, is crucial even with balanced datasets. The observed complementary strengths (transformers excelling in semantic fluency tasks and traditional ML models performing best on narrative tasks) highlight the potential for ensemble methods that combine these approaches. Integrating additional modalities beyond acoustic and linguistic features, such as facial expressions, eye movements, or physiological markers, could further enhance detection accuracy through multimodal deep learning architectures, offering a more comprehensive approach to cognitive impairment detection.

Bibliography

- Agbavor, F. and Liang, H. (2024). Multilingual prediction of cognitive impairment with large language models and speech analysis. *Brain sciences*, 14(12):1292.
- Akiba, T., Sano, S., Yanase, T., Ohta, T., and Koyama, M. (2019). Optuna: A next-generation hyperparameter optimization framework. In *Proceedings of the 25th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery & Data Mining*, page 2623–2631. Association for Computing Machinery.
- Alzheimer’s Association (2021). 2021 alzheimer’s disease facts and figures. *Alzheimer’s & Dementia*, 17(3):1–104.
- Alzheimer’s Society (2024). Facts for the media about dementia. Retrieved November 18, 2024, from <https://www.alzheimers.org.uk/about-us/news-and-media/facts-media>.
- Amlerova, J., Laczó, J., Nedelska, Z., Laczó, M., Vyhnálek, M., Zhang, B., Sheardova, K., Angelucci, F., Andel, R., and Hort, J. (2022). Emotional prosody recognition is impaired in alzheimer’s disease. *Alzheimer’s Research & Therapy*, 14(1):50.
- Arvanitakis, Z., Shah, R. C., and Bennett, D. A. (2019). Diagnosis and management of dementia: Review. *JAMA*, 322(16):1589–1599.
- Asperholm, M., Högman, N., Rafi, J., and Herlitz, A. (2019). What did you do yesterday? a meta-analysis of sex differences in episodic memory. *Psychological bulletin*, 145(8):785.
- Bergstra, J., Bardenet, R., Bengio, Y., and Kégl, B. (2011). Algorithms for hyper-parameter optimization. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 24*, pages 2546–2554.
- Blennow, K. (2017). A review of fluid biomarkers for alzheimer’s disease: moving from csf to blood. *Neurology and therapy*, 6:15–24.
- Brooks, B. L., Iverson, G. L., Holdnack, J. A., and Feldman, H. H. (2008). Potential for misclassification of mild cognitive impairment: A study of memory scores on the wechsler memory scale-iii in healthy older adults. *Journal of the International Neuropsychological Society*, 14(3):463–478.

- Chen, Y., Argentinis, J. E., and Weber, G. (2016). Ibm watson: how cognitive computing can be applied to big data challenges in life sciences research. *Clinical therapeutics*, 38(4):688–701.
- Cintoli, S., Favilli, L., Morganti, R., Siciliano, G., Ceravolo, R., and Tognoni, G. (2024). Verbal fluency patterns associated with the amnesic conversion from mild cognitive impairment to dementia. *Scientific Reports*, 14(1):2029.
- Clouston, S. A., Hanes, D. W., Smith, D. M., Richmond, L. L., Richards, M., and Link, B. (2024). Inequalities in accelerated cognitive decline: Resolving observational window bias using nested non-linear regression. *Alzheimer's & Dementia*, 20(8):5540–5550.
- Cunningham, E. L., McGuinness, B., Herron, B., and Passmore, P. A. (2015). Dementia. *The Ulster Medical Journal*, 84(2):79–87.
- Devlin, J., Chang, M.-W., Lee, K., and Toutanova, K. (2019). Bert: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding. In *Proceedings of the 2019 conference of the North American chapter of the association for computational linguistics: human language technologies, volume 1 (long and short papers)*, pages 4171–4186.
- Drummond, C., Coutinho, G., Fonseca, R. P., Assunção, N., Teldeschi, A., de Oliveira-Souza, R., Moll, J., Tovar-Moll, F., and Mattos, P. (2015). Deficits in narrative discourse elicited by visual stimuli are already present in patients with mild cognitive impairment. *Frontiers in aging neuroscience*, 7:96.
- Dunne, R. A., Aarsland, D., O'Brien, J. T., Ballard, C., Banerjee, S., Fox, N. C., Isaacs, J. D., Underwood, B. R., Perry, R. J., Chan, D., et al. (2021). Mild cognitive impairment: the manchester consensus. *Age and ageing*, 50(1):72–80.
- Eyben, F., Wöllmer, M., and Schuller, B. (2010). Opensmile: the munich versatile and fast open-source audio feature extractor. In *Proceedings of the 18th ACM international conference on Multimedia*, pages 1459–1462.
- Folstein, M. F., Folstein, S. E., and McHugh, P. R. (1975). “mini-mental state”: a practical method for grading the cognitive state of patients for the clinician. *Journal of psychiatric research*, 12(3):189–198.
- Forbes-McKay, K. E. and Venneri, A. (2005). Detecting subtle spontaneous language decline in early alzheimer's disease with a picture description task. *Neurological sciences*, 26:243–254.
- Frisoni, G. B., Fox, N. C., Jack Jr, C. R., Scheltens, P., and Thompson, P. M. (2010). The clinical use of structural mri in alzheimer disease. *Nature reviews neurology*, 6(2):67–77.
- Goodglass, H., Kaplan, E., and Barresi, B. (2001). *The assessment of aphasia and related disorders*. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.

- Gosztolya, G., Balogh, R., Imre, N., Egas-Lopez, J. V., Hoffmann, I., Vincze, V., Tóth, L., Devanand, D. P., Pákási, M., and Kálmán, J. (2021). Cross-lingual detection of mild cognitive impairment based on temporal parameters of spontaneous speech. *Computer Speech & Language*, 69:101215.
- Gosztolya, G. and Tóth, L. (2024). Combining acoustic feature sets for detecting mild cognitive impairment in the interspeech'24 tauskadial challenge. In *Proc. Interspeech 2024*, pages 957–961.
- Gosztolya, G., Vincze, V., Tóth, L., Pákási, M., Kálmán, J., and Hoffmann, I. (2019). Identifying mild cognitive impairment and mild alzheimer's disease based on spontaneous speech using asr and linguistic features. *Computer Speech & Language*, 53:181–197.
- Halder, R. K., Uddin, M. N., Uddin, M. A., Aryal, S., and Khraisat, A. (2024). Enhancing k-nearest neighbor algorithm: a comprehensive review and performance analysis of modifications. *Journal of Big Data*, 11(1):113.
- Hamrick, P., Sanborn, V., Ostrand, R., Gunstad, J., et al. (2023). Lexical speech features of spontaneous speech in older persons with and without cognitive impairment: reliability analysis. *JMIR aging*, 6(1):e46483.
- Han, J. H., Kim, J., Kim, K., and Kim, H. (2018). Emotion recognition and expression in patients with alzheimer's disease. *Journal of Alzheimer's Disease*, 66(3):963–975.
- Huang, K., Altosaar, J., and Ranganath, R. (2019). Clinicalbert: Modeling clinical notes and predicting hospital readmission. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1904.05342*.
- Huang, L., Yang, H., Che, Y., and Yang, J. (2024). Automatic speech analysis for detecting cognitive decline of older adults. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 12:1417966.
- Huang, Z., Lin, H. W., Zhang, Q., and Zong, X. (2022). Targeting alzheimer's disease: the critical crosstalk between the liver and brain. *Nutrients*, 14(20):4298.
- Issitt, R. W., Cortina-Borja, M., Bryant, W., Bowyer, S., Taylor, A. M., Sebire, N., and Bowyer, S. A. (2022). Classification performance of neural networks versus logistic regression models: evidence from healthcare practice. *Cureus*, 14(2).
- Jabbar, H. G. (2024). Advanced threat detection using soft and hard voting techniques in ensemble learning. *Journal of Robotics and Control (JRC)*, 5(4):1104–1116.
- Jack, C. R., Knopman, D. S., Jagust, W. J., Shaw, L. M., Aisen, P. S., Weiner, M. W., Petersen, R. C., and Trojanowski, J. Q. (2010). Hypothetical model of dynamic biomarkers of the alzheimer's pathological cascade. *The Lancet Neurology*, 9(1):119–128.
- Jack Jr, C. R., Bennett, D. A., Blennow, K., Carrillo, M. C., Dunn, B., Haeberlein, S. B., Holtzman, D. M., Jagust, W., Jessen, F., Karlawish, J., et al. (2018). NIA-AA research

- framework: toward a biological definition of alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimer's & dementia*, 14(4):535–562.
- Kabiri, S., Jameie, M., Balali, P., Adib Moradi, S., Sanjari Moghaddam, H., Aghamollai, V., and Harirchian, M. H. (2023). Trail making test could predict impairment in cognitive domains in patients with multiple sclerosis: a study of diagnostic accuracy. *Archives of Clinical Neuropsychology*, 38(1):37–48.
- Kim, B. S., Kim, Y. B., and Kim, H. (2019). Discourse measures to differentiate between mild cognitive impairment and healthy aging. *Frontiers in aging neuroscience*, 11:221.
- Klunk, W. E., Engler, H., Nordberg, A., Wang, Y., Blomqvist, G., Holt, D. P., Bergström, M., Savitcheva, I., Huang, G.-F., Estrada, S., et al. (2004). Imaging brain amyloid in alzheimer's disease with pittsburgh compound-b. *Annals of Neurology: Official Journal of the American Neurological Association and the Child Neurology Society*, 55(3):306–319.
- König, A., Satt, A., Sorin, A., Hoory, R., Toledo-Ronen, O., Derreumaux, A., Manera, V., Verhey, F., Aalten, P., Robert, P. H., et al. (2015). Automatic speech analysis for the assessment of patients with predementia and alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimer's & Dementia: Diagnosis, Assessment & Disease Monitoring*, 1(1):112–124.
- Kourou, K., Exarchos, T. P., Exarchos, K. P., Karamouzis, M. V., and Fotiadis, D. I. (2015). Machine learning applications in cancer prognosis and prediction. *Computational and structural biotechnology journal*, 13:8–17.
- Kramp, S., Cassani, G., and Emmerly, C. (2023). Native language identification with big bird embeddings. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2309.06923*.
- Levine, D. A., Gross, A. L., Briceño, E. M., Tilton, N., Giordani, B. J., Sussman, J. B., Hayward, R. A., Burke, J. F., Hingtgen, S., Elkind, M. S., et al. (2021). Sex differences in cognitive decline among us adults. *JAMA network open*, 4(2):e210169–e210169.
- Liu, Y., Ott, M., Goyal, N., Du, J., Joshi, M., Chen, D., Levy, O., Lewis, M., Zettlemoyer, L., and Stoyanov, V. (2019). Roberta: A robustly optimized bert pretraining approach. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1907.11692*.
- Luz, S., Haider, F., de la Fuente, S., Fromm, D., and MacWhinney, B. (2021). Detecting cognitive decline using speech only: The addresso challenge. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2104.09356*.
- Mao, R., Lin, C., and Guerin, F. (2021). Combining pre-trained word embeddings and linguistic features for sequential metaphor identification. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2104.03285*.
- McKhann, G. M., Knopman, D. S., Chertkow, H., Hyman, B. T., Jack Jr, C. R., Kawas, C. H., Klunk, W. E., Koroshetz, W. J., Manly, J. J., Mayeux, R., et al. (2011). The diagnosis of dementia due to alzheimer's disease: Recommendations from the national institute on

- aging-alzheimer's association workgroups on diagnostic guidelines for alzheimer's disease. *Alzheimer's & dementia*, 7(3):263–269.
- Mielke, M. M., Aggarwal, N. T., Vila-Castelar, C., Agarwal, P., Arenaza-Urquijo, E. M., Brett, B., Brugulat-Serrat, A., DuBose, L. E., Eikelboom, W. S., Flatt, J., et al. (2022). Consideration of sex and gender in alzheimer's disease and related disorders from a global perspective. *Alzheimer's & dementia*, 18(12):2707–2724.
- Mirheidari, B., O'Malley, R., Blackburn, D., and Christensen, H. (2023). Identifying people with mild cognitive impairment at risk of developing dementia using speech analysis. In *2023 IEEE Automatic Speech Recognition and Understanding Workshop (ASRU)*, pages 1–6. IEEE.
- Mirheidari, B., Pan, Y., Blackburn, D., O'Malley, R., and Christensen, H. (2021). Identifying cognitive impairment using sentence representation vectors. In *Interspeech*, pages 2941–2945.
- Molinuevo, J. L., Ayton, S., Batrla, R., Bednar, M. M., Bittner, T., Cummings, J., Fagan, A. M., Hampel, H., Mielke, M. M., Mikulskis, A., et al. (2018). Current state of alzheimer's fluid biomarkers. *Acta neuropathologica*, 136:821–853.
- Mosconi, L., Tsui, W. H., Herholz, K., Pupi, A., Drzezga, A., Lucignani, G., Reiman, E. M., Holthoff, V., Kalbe, E., Sorbi, S., et al. (2008). Multicenter standardized 18f-fdg pet diagnosis of mild cognitive impairment, alzheimer's disease, and other dementias. *Journal of nuclear medicine*, 49(3):390–398.
- Mueller, K. D., Hermann, B., Mecollari, J., and Turkstra, L. S. (2018). Connected speech and language in mild cognitive impairment and alzheimer's disease: A review of picture description tasks. *Journal of clinical and experimental neuropsychology*, 40(9):917–939.
- Nagendran, M., Chen, Y., Lovejoy, C. A., Gordon, A. C., Komorowski, M., Harvey, H., Topol, E. J., Ioannidis, J. P., Collins, G. S., and Maruthappu, M. (2020). Artificial intelligence versus clinicians: systematic review of design, reporting standards, and claims of deep learning studies. *bmj*, 368.
- Nasreddine, Z. S., Phillips, N. A., Bédirian, V., Charbonneau, S., Whitehead, V., Collin, I., Cummings, J. L., and Chertkow, H. (2005). The montreal cognitive assessment, moca: a brief screening tool for mild cognitive impairment. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, 53(4):695–699.
- National Health Service (2023). What is dementia. <https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/dementia/about-dementia/what-is-dementia/>.
- Oikonomou, E. K. and Khera, R. (2023). Machine learning in precision diabetes care and cardiovascular risk prediction. *Cardiovascular Diabetology*, 22(1):259.

- Pedregosa, F., Varoquaux, G., Gramfort, A., Michel, V., Thirion, B., Grisel, O., Blondel, M., Prettenhofer, P., Weiss, R., Dubourg, V., et al. (2011). Scikit-learn: Machine learning in python. *the Journal of machine Learning research*, 12:2825–2830.
- Petersen, R. C. (2016). Mild cognitive impairment. *CONTINUUM: lifelong Learning in Neurology*, 22(2):404–418.
- Petersen, R. C. and Negash, S. (2008). Mild cognitive impairment: an overview. *CNS spectrums*, 13(1):45–53.
- Poppe, M., Mansour, H., Rapaport, P., Palomo, M., Burton, A., Morgan-Trimmer, S., Carter, C., Roche, M., Higgs, P., Walker, Z., et al. (2020). “falling through the cracks”; stakeholders’ views around the concept and diagnosis of mild cognitive impairment and their understanding of dementia prevention. *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*, 35(11):1349–1357.
- Ranson, J. M., Kuźma, E., Hamilton, W., Muniz-Terrera, G., Langa, K. M., and Llewellyn, D. J. (2019). Predictors of dementia misclassification when using brief cognitive assessments. *Neurology: Clinical Practice*, 9(2):109–117.
- Reimers, N. and Gurevych, I. (2019). Sentence-bert: Sentence embeddings using siamese bert-networks. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1908.10084*.
- Sabbagh, M. N., Boada, M., Borson, S., Chilukuri, M., Dubois, B., Ingram, J., Iwata, A., Porsteinsson, A., Possin, K., Rabinovici, G., et al. (2020). Early detection of mild cognitive impairment (mci) in primary care. *The Journal of prevention of Alzheimer’s disease*, 7:165–170.
- Sagi, O. and Rokach, L. (2018). Ensemble learning: A survey. *Wiley interdisciplinary reviews: data mining and knowledge discovery*, 8(4):e1249.
- Sainburg, T. and Zorea, A. (2024). Noisereduce: Domain general noise reduction for time series signals. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2412.17851*.
- Sanford, A. M. (2017). Mild cognitive impairment. *Clinics in geriatric medicine*, 33(3):325–337.
- Sanh, V., Debut, L., Chaumond, J., and Wolf, T. (2019). Distilbert, a distilled version of bert: Smaller, faster, cheaper and lighter. arxiv 2019. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1910.01108*.
- Shao, Z., Janse, E., Visser, K., and Meyer, A. S. (2014). What do verbal fluency tasks measure? predictors of verbal fluency performance in older adults. *Frontiers in psychology*, 5:772.
- Taler, V. and Phillips, N. A. (2008). Language performance in alzheimer’s disease and mild cognitive impairment: a comparative review. *Journal of clinical and experimental neuropsychology*, 30(5):501–556.

- Tombaugh, T. N. and McIntyre, N. J. (1992). The mini-mental state examination: a comprehensive review. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, 40(9):922–935.
- Vaswani, A., Shazeer, N., Parmar, N., Uszkoreit, J., Jones, L., Gomez, A. N., Kaiser, L. u., and Polosukhin, I. (2017). Attention is all you need. In Guyon, I., Luxburg, U. V., Bengio, S., Wallach, H., Fergus, R., Vishwanathan, S., and Garnett, R., editors, *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, volume 30. Curran Associates, Inc.
- Wang, Y., Matsushima, T., Matsushima, S., and Sakai, T. (2025). Enhancing and exploring mild cognitive impairment detection with w2v-bert-2.0. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2501.16201*.
- Wechsler, D. (1997). Wechsler adult intelligence scale-. *Frontiers in Psychology*.
- Winblad, B., Amouyel, P., Andrieu, S., Ballard, C., Brayne, C., Brodaty, H., Cedazo-Minguez, A., Dubois, B., Edvardsson, D., Feldman, H., et al. (2016). Defeating alzheimer’s disease and other dementias: a priority for european science and society. *The Lancet Neurology*, 15(5):455–532.
- Wright, L. M., De Marco, M., and Venneri, A. (2023). Current understanding of verbal fluency in alzheimer’s disease: evidence to date. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, pages 1691–1705.
- Yamasaki, T. and Ikeda, T. (2024). Advances in research on brain health and dementia: Prevention and early detection of cognitive decline and dementia. *Brain Sciences*, 14(4):353.
- Yuan, J., Cai, X., Bian, Y., Ye, Z., and Church, K. (2021). Pauses for detection of alzheimer’s disease. *Frontiers in Computer Science*, 2:624488.
- Zetterberg, H. and Blennow, K. (2018). From cerebrospinal fluid to blood: the third wave of fluid biomarkers for alzheimer’s disease. *Journal of Alzheimer’s Disease*, 64(s1):S271–S279.
- Zhang, S., Khlif, N., Ferro, M., Gagliardi, G., and Tamburini, F. (2025). Cognitive decline detection using dlb extraction pipelines. In *ICASSP 2025-2025 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*, pages 1–2. IEEE.

Appendices

Appendix A

Risk Assessment

This appendix outlines the risks identified for the project, their potential consequences, and mitigation strategies. It includes key metrics like likelihood, impact, and risk ratings (Figure A.1) and a detailed risk register (Table A.1) documenting specific risks and residual risks after mitigation. The goal is to ensure effective risk management throughout the project.

Likelihood (L)	Description
5	Very likely/imminent - certain to happen.
4	Probable - a strong possibility of it happening.
3	Possible - it may have happened before.
2	Unlikely - could happen but unusual.
1	Rare - highly unlikely to occur.

(a) Likelihood (L) Description

Impact (I)	Description
5	Catastrophic - non-functional system.
4	Major - significant changes to the system.
3	Moderate - moderate changes to the system.
2	Minor - minor changes to the system.
1	Very minor - very minor changes to the system or requirements.

(b) Impact (I) Description

		Impact (I)				
		1	2	3	4	5
Likelihood (L)	5	5	10	15	20	25
	4	4	8	12	16	20
	3	3	6	9	12	15
	2	2	4	6	8	10
	1	1	2	3	4	5

(c) Impact-Likelihood Matrix

Risk Rating (RR)	Action
High Risk	Stop the task/activity until controls are in place to reduce the risk.
Medium Risk	Determine further precautions to reduce the risk.
Low Risk	No further action; keep under review.

(d) Risk Rating (RR) Actions

Figure A.1: Risk Rating Keys Description

Table A.1: Detailed Project Risk Register

ID	Consequences	L	I	RR	Control Measures	Res. L	Res. I	Res. RR
1	Unauthorized access to sensitive participant data could breach privacy and violate ethical standards	2	5	10	Store data on secure, encrypted systems with access control; do not share identifiable data publicly	1	5	5
2	Inadequate anonymization of audio or transcripts risks exposing participant identities or personal details	2	4	8	Remove or mask personal identifiers in data (e.g., names in transcripts); never distribute raw identifiable audio	1	4	4
3	Failure to comply with ethical data handling protocols could lead to project suspension or legal issues	2	5	10	Adhere strictly to approved guidelines (authorized personnel only, no external data sharing, etc.) and review compliance regularly	1	5	5
4	Using data beyond the scope of participant consent (or without proper permission) can cause ethical and legal violations	1	4	4	Ensure project activities remain within consented use; seek additional ethics approval for any scope expansion	1	2	2
5	Dataset or software license restrictions may limit use or sharing, hindering collaboration or publication	1	3	3	Verify licenses and usage rights early; use only data and tools that permit intended research use and result dissemination	1	1	1
6	Not destroying or properly disposing of data after the project could lead to future privacy breaches	2	3	6	Plan for secure deletion of all sensitive data upon project completion and document the data disposal	1	3	3

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ID	Consequences	L	I	RR	Control Measures	Res. L	Res. I	Res. RR
7	Model bias or unfair performance (e.g., varying accuracy across demographics) may lead to ethical and validity concerns	3	4	12	Evaluate model fairness across subgroups; if bias is detected, adjust training (rebalance data or tweak model) and report limitations	2	4	8
8	Unplanned need for new ethics approval (due to scope change) could halt work until approval is obtained	2	4	8	Define project scope clearly and avoid mid-project changes requiring new approvals; if needed, initiate ethics applications early	1	4	4
9	Insufficient training data may lead to overfitting and unreliable model results	5	4	20	Augment dataset or combine datasets; apply cross-validation and regularization to mitigate overfitting	4	3	12
10	Poor data quality (noisy audio or transcript errors) could result in misleading features and degraded model accuracy	3	3	9	Preprocess and clean data (filter noise, correct transcripts) to improve quality; remove unusable samples	2	3	6
11	Imbalanced dataset can skew the classifier towards the majority class, reducing detection of minority (MCI) cases	4	4	16	Use stratified sampling, class weighting or data augmentation to balance classes during training	2	3	6
12	Dataset not representative of the broader population may limit generalizability of the findings to other groups	4	3	12	Include diverse data if possible or acknowledge this limitation; avoid overgeneralizing conclusions	4	2	8

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ID	Consequences	L	I	RR	Control Measures	Res. L	Res. I	Res. RR
13	Missing or incomplete data (e.g., some recordings or metadata) could undermine analyses or reduce sample size	3	2	6	Identify and address gaps early (impute missing values or exclude incomplete cases consistently)	1	2	2
14	Inaccurate labels or transcription errors could mislead the model training and evaluation results	2	3	6	Cross-verify data labels with clinical scores; manually review and correct sample transcripts as needed	2	2	4
15	Dependence on external data providers (CognoSpeak team) might delay data access or updates, stalling progress	2	4	8	Request required datasets early and maintain communication with data owners; have fallback datasets if possible	1	4	4
16	Complex acoustic feature extractor (OpenSMILE) misconfiguration might yield incorrect or irrelevant features	3	3	9	Use well-documented feature sets (e.g., eGeMAPS); validate extracted features on sample audio and consult documentation or experts	1	3	3
17	Challenges in extracting linguistic features (e.g., parsing transcripts) could result in incomplete or trivial text data	3	2	6	Leverage existing NLP tools or embeddings for text analysis; pilot test linguistic feature extraction on transcripts to ensure quality	1	2	2
18	Difficulty merging acoustic and linguistic pipelines may delay or prevent multimodal analysis	3	4	12	Start with simple fusion methods (feature concatenation or late fusion) before attempting complex integration; ensure data formats are compatible	2	3	6

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ID	Consequences	L	I	RR	Control Measures	Res. L	Res. I	Res. RR
19	Bugs in model training code or data processing scripts could produce invalid results or waste time debugging	4	3	12	Test code modules with small datasets; use version control and debugging tools to catch errors early in the development	2	3	6
20	Software/library incompatibilities (version conflicts or OS issues) might disrupt development or model training	3	3	9	Use a consistent environment (e.g., container or virtual env) with tested library versions; avoid unnecessary upgrades mid-project	2	2	4
21	Steep learning curve for new frameworks (PyTorch, HuggingFace) could slow development and cause implementation mistakes	3	2	6	Practice on smaller examples (completed a speaker ID task) and consult online resources/community to build proficiency	1	2	2
22	Misinterpretation of analysis outputs or visualizations can lead to wrong conclusions about model performance	2	4	8	Use multiple evaluation metrics and have results reviewed (by supervisor or peers) to ensure correct interpretation	1	4	4
23	Lack of a reproducible pipeline (inconsistent results across runs or environments) could undermine confidence in findings	3	2	6	Document the pipeline thoroughly and use consistent random seeds; test the entire process on a fresh environment to ensure reproducibility	1	2	2
24	Models overfitting the training data would perform poorly on new data, invalidating the experimental results	4	4	16	Apply regularization, cross-validation, and keep model complexity in check (stop training early if overfitting observed)	2	4	8

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ID	Consequences	L	I	RR	Control Measures	Res. L	Res. I	Res. RR
25	Models underfitting (failing to learn patterns) would yield low accuracy, contributing little insight	3	3	9	Ensure features are informative and try more complex models or tuning if simple models underperform; verify model capacity matches problem complexity	1	3	3
26	Suboptimal hyperparameter selection can prevent models from reaching peak performance	3	2	6	Use bayesian hyperparameter tuning (e.g Optuna TPE sampler with cross-validation) and base ranges on literature or prior experiments	2	2	4
27	Using inappropriate evaluation metrics (e.g., only accuracy in imbalanced data) could give a false sense of model success	2	3	6	Adopt relevant metrics (precision, recall, F1, AUC) alongside accuracy; examine confusion matrices for a complete performance picture	1	3	3
28	Training convergence issues (model not converging or diverging) would waste time and yield no usable model	2	3	6	Monitor training loss curves; adjust learning rates or algorithms if divergence is detected, and use pre-trained weights for stable starting points	1	2	2
29	Model may latch onto spurious correlations in the data, making predictions that won't generalize (fragile model)	3	4	12	Perform feature importance analysis to detect any single dominating feature; ensure data and features are vetted for confounders	2	4	8
30	Multimodal fusion might not yield improvement if one modality dominates or the fusion method is ineffective	4	3	12	Evaluate each modality independently as baseline; try different fusion strategies (early vs. late fusion) and ensure proper feature scaling	3	2	6

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ID	Consequences	L	I	RR	Control Measures	Res. L	Res. I	Res. RR
31	Accidental data leakage (e.g., test data inadvertently used in training) would inflate performance metrics unrealistically	3	5	15	Use strict train/test splits at participant level and double-check data pipelines to ensure no overlap; isolate test dataset early	1	5	5
32	Pre-trained LLMs might not adapt well to limited domain data, resulting in minimal performance gains over simpler models	4	3	12	Fine-tune domain-specific models (e.g., ClinicalBERT) and use techniques like layer freezing to cope with small data; rely on classical models as robust baseline	3	2	6
33	High latency or slow model performance might disrupt clinical workflows, making real-time use infeasible	3	2	6	Optimize model efficiency (use smaller models or efficient hardware); if needed, perform computations offline or in batch to reduce wait times	2	2	4
34	Data format or compatibility issues between the research model and clinical data systems could impede integration	3	2	6	Use standard data formats (e.g., common audio formats and transcript standards); ensure required input data is routinely collected in clinical settings	1	2	2
35	Improper user trust calibration – either over-reliance or disregard – could lead to misuses or underutilization of the tool	3	3	9	Provide confidence levels with predictions and training for users on appropriate use; emphasize that the tool is a decision support, not a definitive diagnosis	2	3	6

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ID	Consequences	L	I	RR	Control Measures	Res. L	Res. I	Res. RR
36	Differences in real clinical environment (background noise, microphone quality) could reduce model accuracy compared to lab results	3	4	12	Test the model with noisy or varied audio conditions; adjust the model (noise-robust features or retraining) or specify operating conditions for reliable use	2	4	8
37	Requirement for specialized hardware or software in clinics (e.g., GPU, high-quality mic) could hinder the tool’s practicality	3	3	9	Ensure the final model can run on standard clinic hardware or provide alternative models that could be run on resource constrained environment	2	3	6
38	Limited availability of GPU/HPC resources can slow experimentation, risking incomplete model tuning	4	3	12	Plan computing tasks efficiently (batch experiments, use off-peak hours); simplify models if necessary to reduce computational load	3	3	9
39	Hardware failure (e.g., GPU crash or disk failure) could interrupt experiments and result in data or progress loss	2	4	8	Regularly backup code (via version control) and data (in approved environment); checkpoint training progress frequently and have alternative hardware options (or another machine) available	1	4	4
40	Excessive training time for models (especially LLMs) could impede completing enough experiments or iterations	4	4	16	Optimize training (use early stopping, fewer epochs if convergence is reached); prioritize critical experiments and utilize any available performance resources	3	3	9
41	Scheduled maintenance or downtime of computing facilities may halt progress during critical periods	3	2	6	Stay informed of maintenance schedules; adjust timeline to complete tasks before downtime or use alternative resources temporarily	1	2	2

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ID	Consequences	L	I	RR	Control Measures	Res. L	Res. I	Res. RR
42	Storage constraints (limited disk space for large audio files and models) could disrupt experiments or data logging	3	2	6	Monitor storage use; compress or archive old results, and request additional storage or use external drives if needed	1	2	2
43	Underestimation of task durations can lead to an overloaded schedule and last-minute rushing	4	4	16	Create a detailed project plan with realistic time estimates and built-in buffers; regularly update the schedule based on progress	2	4	8
44	Unforeseen technical challenges (bugs, data issues) can cause significant delays in the project timeline	3	4	12	Allocate contingency time in the plan for unexpected issues; address critical technical risks early and seek prompt help when blocked	2	4	8
45	Missing key deadlines (e.g., draft submissions or final submission) could jeopardize project completion	2	5	10	Set internal interim deadlines ahead of official ones; monitor progress and adjust workload to ensure all deliverables are ready on time	1	5	5
46	Scope creep (adding new features or analyses beyond original plan) might overwhelm resources and timeline	3	3	9	Strictly adhere to defined objectives; log new ideas for future work instead of expanding current scope without time to accommodate it	1	3	3
47	Illness or other personal issues affecting the sole researcher could halt progress and threaten deadlines	2	5	10	Maintain healthy work habits and communicate with supervisors early if issues arise; if needed, arrange extensions or assistance proactively	2	4	8

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ID	Consequences	L	I	RR	Control Measures	Res. L	Res. I	Res. RR
48	Miscommunication with the supervisor may lead to working in a wrong direction or missing expectations	3	4	12	Have regular meetings to get feedback; clarify goals and deliverables in writing (emails or meeting minutes) to ensure mutual understanding	1	4	4
49	Poor communication with the CognoSpeak team could result in misunderstandings about data use or integration	2	3	6	Provide periodic updates to the team; confirm any assumptions regarding data and tool integration requirements with them	1	3	3
50	Lack of progress tracking and project management could allow issues to go unnoticed until it's too late to fix	3	3	9	Use a project management tool or timeline to regularly review completed tasks vs. plan; adjust plans as needed to stay on track	1	3	3
51	Imbalanced time allocation (focusing on coding over evaluation or writing) could reduce overall project quality	3	4	12	Follow the project plan to allocate time for each phase; set milestones for analysis and writing, not just development	2	3	6
52	Leaving the dissertation write-up to the last minute can result in a rushed document with omissions or poor clarity	4	3	12	Write continuously alongside development (document methods, keep notes); set early draft deadlines for each chapter to allow time for revisions	2	3	6
53	The project may fail to produce any significant results (e.g., models barely above chance) undermining its success	3	5	15	Pursue multiple approaches to increase chances of insights (different models, features); thoroughly analyze even negative results to extract lessons or patterns	2	4	8

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ID	Consequences	L	I	RR	Control Measures	Res. L	Res. I	Res. RR
54	Results may not be easily reproducible by others, calling into question their reliability and scientific validity	3	4	12	Ensure all experiments are well-documented with fixed random seeds and methodology details; share code and data where possible for verification	1	4	4
55	The research contribution might be deemed too incremental or lacking novelty, affecting its academic impact	3	3	9	Highlight any novel aspects (new dataset usage, method combination) in writing; compare with recent works to clearly delineate contributions	2	3	6
56	Conclusions or claims in the thesis that are not fully supported by data could weaken the credibility of the work	2	4	8	Base all claims on presented evidence; have the supervisor review the conclusion section to ensure all statements are justified by results	1	3	3
57	Inadequate documentation (code or methodology) could make it hard for others to understand or reuse the work	4	2	8	Comment code clearly and write a detailed methodology section; provide guidelines for replicating experiments in an appendix or repository	2	2	4
58	Emerging research during the project could overshadow this work or require adjustments to avoid duplication	2	3	6	Continuously monitor new publications in the field; be prepared to adjust emphasis or incorporate comparative discussion to maintain relevance	2	2	4
59	Not all project objectives may be met (e.g., some planned experiments dropped), which could reduce the thesis scope	3	4	12	Focus on core objectives first; if time runs short, document unmet goals as future work rather than attempting all objectives poorly	2	3	6

Appendix B

Configuration Examples

This appendix presents example YAML configuration files used in the experimental framework of this study.

```
1 # Audio Processing Config
2 audio_processing:
3   denoise:
4     enabled: True
5     noisereduce_params:
6       stationary: False
7       prop_decrease: 0.75
8       n_std_thresh_stationary: 1.5
9       time_mask_smooth_ms: 200
10
11   args:
12     data_dir: "/path/example"
13
14 # Transcript Processing Config
15 transcript_processing:
16   special_tokens:
17     enable: false
18     level: "sentence"
19   tokens:
20     - SPS
21     - LPS
22
23   args:
24     data_dir: "/path/example"
25     tasks: [ "CTD", "SFT", "PFT" ]
26     target_speaker: "Pat"
27     remove_punctuations: false
28     remove_fillers: false
29     to_lowercase: false
30     output_folder: "/path/example"
```

Listing B.1: Example YAML configuration file for audio preprocessing

```
1 # Acoustic Feature Extraction Config
2 acoustic_feature_extraction:
3   opensmile:
4     feature_set: "ComParE_2016"
5     feature_level: "Functionals"
6
7   args:
8     data_dir: "/path/example"
9     metadata_file: "/path/example/metadata.csv"
10    tasks: [ "CTD" ]
11    splits: [ "test" ]
12    output_folder: "/path/example"
13    output_file: "CTD_test_ComParE_2016_Functionals.csv"
14
15
16 # Linguistic Feature Extraction Config
17 linguistic_feature_extraction:
18   sbert:
19     model: "bert-base-uncased"
20     level: 1
21     spacy_model: "en_core_web_sm"
22
23   args:
24     tasks: [ "PFT" ]
25     splits: [ "test" ]
26     data_dir: "/path/example"
27     metadata_file: "/path/example/metadata.csv"
28     output_folder: "/path/example"
29     output_file: "PFT_test.csv"
```

Listing B.2: Example YAML configuration file for feature extraction

```
1
2 # Transformer Model Training Config
3 language_model:
4   dataset:
5     train_data_path: "/example/tran.csv"
6     test_data_path: "/example/test.csv"
7     num_labels: 2
8     text_column: "text"
9     label_column: "class"
10    shuffle: true
11
12  tokenizer:
13    max_length: 512
14    padding: "max_length"
15    truncation: true
16    return_tensors: "pt"
17
18  training_args:
19    seed: 55
20    output_dir: "./trainer_output"
21    learning_rate: 3e-05
22    num_train_epochs: 20
23
24  hyperparameter_search:
25    n_trials: 100
26    n_splits: 5
27    is_stratified: true
28    eval_metric: "eval_f1"
29
30  train_cv:
31    n_splits: 5
32    is_stratified: true
33
34  args:
35    run_mode: train
36    model_name_or_path: "bert-base-uncased"
37    random_seed: 55
38    additional_special_tokens: ['<SPS>', '<LPS>']
39    save_artifacts: true
40    save_model_name: "CTD_bert-base-uncased"
41    scoring_average: macro
42    output_dir: "./artifacts"
```

Listing B.3: Example YAML configuration file for transformer model fine-tuning

Appendix C

Raw Experimental Results

This appendix provides access to the comprehensive experimental results from all pipelines developed in this study. For transparency and reproducibility purposes, detailed performance metrics for each model configuration, including those not fully presented in the main text due to space constraints, are available in online spreadsheets.

Table C.1: Links to Raw Experimental Results

Pipeline	Results Link
Pipeline A: Acoustic ML	Access Results
Pipeline B: Linguistic ML	Access Results
Pipeline C: Transformer Models	Access Results
Pipeline D: Ensemble Approach	Access Results
Ablation Studies	Access Results